

D4.1 - REPORT PRESENTING SCENARIOS AND RELATED POLICY PACKAGES

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Abstract

The transition from linear, fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and an appropriate pathway to achieve several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems represent a great opportunity to reconcile long-term sustainable growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This necessary transition is a complex process that requires not only innovative supply-side technologies, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate for proposing a new economic model, requiring transformative policies, targeted innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity, and new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy and the potential for improvement associated with circular bio-based systems is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Against this background, SUSTRACK is a three-year project that aims to support policy makers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems (at EU and regional level), thus contributing to the objectives of the European Green Deal. This will be done by: Identifying the environmental, economic, and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing different transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to the scenarios analysed in the project and developing guidelines and policy recommendations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of this report (D4.1) is to identify and describe policy goals that are essential for the transformation to a circular biobased economy, and to develop policy portfolio scenarios for the four focus sectors of the project: construction, chemicals, plastics and textiles. This work on policy goals and scenarios supports the development of the Green Economy Model in WP4, and the identification of policy priorities in WP5. The scenarios formulated and presented in this report also support more detailed research to be carried out for the case studies to be analysed in each sector.

The report provides an overview of the different steps implemented for data collection and scenario development. Concerning data gathering, screening criteria for the adequate identification of policy goals impacting the evolution of circular biobased economy have been elaborated. Further, a template was prepared that summarises the parameters necessary to collect for the implementation of the scenarios in the GEM model (i.e. model inputs) as well as to generate a portfolio of policy goals. An overview of the collected and selected policy objectives included in the scenarios is provided in short fact sheets, one for each policy document. The scenarios are described at the EU level, including sector specific policy goals as well as more general cross sectoral and macroeconomic goals. For each, two scenarios have been developed. The BioTransition scenario considers existing, status quo policy objectives. The BioRevolution scenario integrates new and more ambitious goals, aiming at a rapid transformation towards a fully circular bio-based economy.

The deliverable begins with the introduction of the methodology adopted for the identification of a portfolio of policy goals and the development of the scenarios. The results section provides an overview of the selected policy goals. Based on the screening of 49 policy documents, expert consultations and verification via stakeholder workshops, 73 policy goals were identified and selected. Building on these goals, one BioTransition and one BioRevolution policy portfolio scenario at the EU level and applied to each sector (chemicals, construction, plastics and textiles) have been generated, for a total of 8 scenarios.

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List of abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
CBBE	Circular biobased economy
CCU	Carbon capture and use
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
EU	European Union
FAQ	Frequently asked questions
GEM	Green Economy Model
GHG	Greenhouse gas emission
LULUCF	Land use, land use change and forestry
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

The bioeconomy is seen as a central approach for reaching the EU's ambition to become climate neutral by 2050 and to support sustainable development (1). After 12 years of strategy development at the EU level, it becomes more evident that a sustainable bioeconomy will be an enabler for a cross-sectoral transformation of the three dimensions of sustainability: environment, economy and society (2). While this cross-sectoral and multi-dimensional perspective is an inherent characteristic of the bioeconomy, it is already clear that the concept of a bioeconomy has to be customised to different country contexts, considering both raw material availability as well as resource use. As a result, there cannot be a single bioeconomy, but many of them -with due customization- across the world, as well as across EU countries, and even across industrial sectors within the same country (2). Although being quite different in different contexts, it is clear that bioeconomy could support the adoption of sustainable production systems while contributing to the mitigation of climate change impacts. While the broader concept of the bioeconomy is still under discussion (3, 4), it is clear that it is linked directly to the circular bio-based economy (CBBE) (5, 6). For example, this connection is established by the definition of the EU bioeconomy strategy: "(...) To be successful, the European bioeconomy needs to have sustainability and circularity at its heart. This will drive the renewal of our industries, the modernisation of our primary production systems, the protection of the environment and will enhance biodiversity" (1). The circular economy as such is characterised by recycling and reduction objectives in contrast to the linear fossil-based economy along the "take-make-consume-throw away" pattern (6). The aim is to develop an economy "where value of products, materials, and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste minimised, is an essential contribution to the EU's efforts to develop a sustainable, low carbon resource-efficient and competitive economy" (7).

The integration of the two aspects of (i) valorisation of biogenic resources and (ii) circularity is stressed as critical in order to align resource use with the planetary boundaries, to strengthen the EU-based industry, and to deliver high quality, functional and safe products to citizens. Specifically, it addresses two central drivers of the transformation process, (i) the fact that bio-based raw material supply is limited, as well as (ii) the decoupling of economic growth from the use of virgin resources (material efficiency) (6, 8, 9). In the actual state of transition, we see that, at the practical level, bio-based business models and solutions are already entering the market (see SUSTRACK Deliverable D3.1 A case study selection methodology). However, it is clear that for scaling up bio-based concepts, supportive as well as guiding governance structures are required that enable and ensure the fulfilment of those sustainability objectives that are inherent to a circular bioeconomy.

As a starting point for the evaluation, a sectoral perspective could support the development of effective governance structures. This sectoral perspective is just a sub-system of the overall bioeconomy and it is called the circular bio-based economy. In this task, the contextualisation will be done in a macro level perspective with the aim to ensure that policies stimulate a faster transformation towards a bio-economy (10) and to assess their impact on the selected bio-based concepts as well as visa versa. The following deliverable of WP4 will focus on estimating the socio-economic and environmental outcomes of policy implementation, using the Green Economy Model (GEM).

1.1 Objective of the report

This report provides an overview of the work that has been performed during Task 4.1. The objective of the report is to develop portfolio policy scenarios, including policy goals, that address the policy area of the Circular Bio-Based Economy in the EU and in selected case study countries. The collected goals are used to create policy portfolios that will inform the development of the Green Economy Model (GEM). By means of simulation, GEM will be used to assess the complementarity of transition outcomes at the EU level, simulating the realisation of national and regional policy goals. In the report, findings obtained during the development of the scenarios for the case study sectors (WP3 and WP5) and the EU level, are presented and discussed. The scenarios are used for the contextualisation of the previously identified case studies, as well as support the assessment of existing and new policy goals in the area of the CBBE.

The goals of the report are the following:

1. Develop scenarios for selected sectors and countries,
2. Provide context for the case study analysis in the other work packages and support the integration of the bio-based solution into a national and EU level policy field,
3. Informing Task 4.2 and 4.3 on the necessary policy goals to be implemented in the Green Economy Model (GEM) to assess the transformation outcomes of more circular bio-based economy policies,
4. Provide information to Task 5.1 on the policy priorities that are in focus to support the achievement of the policy objectives in the formulated scenarios,
5. Generate a portfolio database of key policy goals for the circular bio-based economy on EU level and country level.

1.2 Structure of the report

The remainder of the report is structured as following: Chapter 2 illustrates the methodological approach used for scenario development; Chapter 3 presents the results of the literature review on policies for the specific sectoral scenarios; Chapter 4 illustrates the scenarios and their characteristics; Chapter 5 closes the report by summarising the main findings and key aspects of the portfolio scenarios, and outlines the next steps within the SUSTRACK project.

2 METHODS

The generation of scenarios followed five key steps, as illustrated in the following overview.

Figure 1: Methodological steps for the elaboration of the scenario formulation

2.1 Scenario scope identification

Scenario work aims to describe possible future pathways, with focus on the interrelation of the aspects included. While the integrated aspects of the scenario development are different for each specific context, the methodological elaboration is to be aligned along the quality criteria of plausibility, consistency, comprehensibility and traceability, distinctness and especially transparency (11, 12).

The first step in scenario development is to describe the general scenario scope. This context description contains information about the objectives, project scope, scenario types as well as the scenario components (13). In this step, the scenario scope is delineated, whereby the information provided remains quite general. Scenarios are used as a method to describe possible future pathways of specific aspects under review. They are narratives of alternative environments, a possible and plausible view of the future world described in storylines and assumptions. They are not predictions nor forecasts, or an exact picture of the future, and cannot include all components of a system (11, 13).

Policy portfolio scenarios are used for broad strategic policy development with the aim to influence actions of large groups of actors or domains (13). Within these dimensions, policy goals that support the transformation of sectors from a linear to a circular bio-based model are identified and compiled. The focus sectors are hereby chemicals, construction, plastics and textiles. The policy portfolio scenarios are based on the current status quo of policy at EU, national and sectoral level, whereby possible future portfolios of policies are based on both documents as well as stakeholder feedback and targets provided. It should be noted that not all policies identified are considered. The portfolio of policies integrated in the scenarios will be analysed for their interactions and interrelations in the modelling step, and the results from this step provide information concerning their specific impacts. For this purpose, it is necessary to set, in the next steps, the boundary conditions for the selection of relevant policies and targets, and their analysis.

2.2 Selection of focus countries for the case study sectors

Case studies in the project scope are understood as a specific value chain, a specific product or a combination of both including different scales covering a whole sub-sector in a region (see SUSTRACK D3.1). The case studies have a high regional impact that is not possible to assess in detail in the policy portfolio scenarios and the model. The portfolio policy scenarios focus on specific sectors and countries. The countries have been chosen based on their potential to have high impact for a transformation to circular biobased economy along the following three criteria:

1. Importance of the sector (i.e. contribution of sectors to the national economy and selection of the case studies in previous WPs)
2. Total size of the economy
3. GHG emissions by sector at EU level

According to these criteria, countries are selected. This assumes that a change in this country would have the greatest impact on future material flows and their circularity.

2.3 Elaboration of screening criteria for policy identification

There are several existing policies that cover a wide variety of system components, with emphasis on all social, economic and environmental targets. Therefore, if portfolios of relevant policies should be compiled, it is necessary to set boundaries for selection criteria. The project focus is on the four sectors of chemicals, construction, plastics and textiles, and the previously identified case studies of the project, to illustrate the potential for a future circular biobased economy. Therefore, the criteria for the screening of policy documents are aligned to the circular economy strategy and the circular economy action plan of the EU (7, 14).

In addition to the specific function of supporting the review process, the screening criteria could also be understood as objectives for the overall policy field of the future CBBE. While the focus on the information gathering is specifically on policy goals, it is necessary to differentiate between different levels of policies in a specific policy field. For the policy portfolio scenarios, the factors are collected from a macro level perspective. For the collection of macro level goals, the policy field is separated into policy objectives, goals and instruments (15).

The policy objectives are more or less the screening criteria. Policy goals as such, are desired future conditions or states to be achieved, ideally in quantitative terms. These are often long term oriented, such as for instance a 30% target for the use of recycled plastic in beverage bottles by 2030 (16). This long-term focus distinguishes this specific target from policy instruments that are more medium-term in nature. They are used as milestones in time to support the achievement of specific policy goals. Policy instruments are the measures how policies are implemented, about which more information will be provided in WP5. In WP5, policy priorities are analysed to achieve the scenario goals and analyses in exchange with model outcomes the specific impact of them.

2.4 Template development for collection and selection of policy goals

Policy goals are collected for the policy portfolio scenarios. This is done using specific parameters (see Table 1) that are compiled in a template developed for this task. The focus for collection and selection is on quantitative goals and their context for the implementation in the GEM in Task 4.2

and 4.3. The specific parameters have been elaborated in an iterative process with the modelling task.

Data gathering is conducted via an extensive literature review of policy strategies, policy directives, regulations, sector strategies and national strategies and energy and climate plans. The desk research and selection process of policy goals was complemented by an expert consultation in the project consortium, and by a stakeholder verification workshop at the INSPIRE conference (see **Error! Reference source not found.** Figure A2 1: Input collected for the plastic sector in the INSPIRE conference Figure A2 1 - Figure A2 4). The verification process in the stakeholder workshop was done via a discussion of selected policy goals (one hour per sector). Based on the responses received, the selection of policy goals was adapted, and new and additional goals were integrated in the scenarios.

Table 1: Content of template for collecting policy goals for the CBBE

Column name	Description
Target name and description	Short name or description for each collected policy goals (e.g. Green Deal, Eco-Design)
Quantitative or qualitative setting	Short description if the goals have a quantitative or qualitative characteristic
Target quantitative or qualitative description	Specific description and citation of identified policy goals from the respective literature
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	If a specific mechanism is described in the selected policy goals is described through which the goal should be reached (not in focus of T4.1, see screening criteria)
Target implementation year (2030, 2050, other)	Year in which the goal should be implemented or achieved
Expected impacts	If a specific impact of reaching the policy goals is indicated
Geographic level (EU, country of the case studies)	Geographical focus area of the policy goal
Sector covered (Textile, Construction, Plastic, Chemicals)	Assignment of the policy goal to a specific project sector or as overarching policy goal that has influence on several sectors
Influenced value chain part	Selection of the part of the value chain that is majorly influenced by the policy goals (production, consumption or end of life)
Reference information	Reference information (policy document name, URL, author, publication year)

2.5 Scenario formulation (Overarching and sector specific)

The aim of the scenario formulation task is to generate a baseline, and a more ambitious and transformative scenario. For each scenario, a portfolio of policy goals was selected. The selected scenario names were developed in an expert consultation, based on three different proposed variants: one focused on the process; one focused on the policies and one focused on the results to be achieved.

The specific policies selected and integrated in the scenarios have been elaborated based on the consultation processes of experts of the project consortium and in the international INSPIRE conference. The suitability of policies and targets, for integration in the modelling exercise, was also considered.

The baseline or reference scenario illustrates the status quo of policies that are identified for the circular biobased economy at the EU and country level. Key issues are identified and scenarios are described based on the collected policies. Further, specific years of implementation (or target years for realising the ambition) are indicated. This supports the consideration of policy targets in the GEM model, making use of time-explicit simulations.

The more ambitious scenario illustrates a faster, more holistic and coherent systemic transformation towards the CBBE. The assumptions for this scenario are elaborated based on literature review, expert consultation in the project consortium, and in the international INSPIRE conference. The data collected have been used to adapt already existing goals to more ambitious ones, as well as adding new goals to the scenario. As an example, in case of quotas, voluntary quotas in discussion are assumed to have regulatory or directive status. Another way is to set the “target implementation year” earlier.

To provide an overview, a table is generated for each scenario showing the policy goals included and the year in which they are implemented. This follows the approach to build a portfolio of policy goals that can be integrated in the model. The advantage of this approach is that the policies could be tested in isolation, as well as integrated into a single simulation. In the more ambitious scenario, the colour for the adapted or added policy goals is blue and the text "Adapted or added policy goals" is added. This helps you to understand the differences between the scenarios quickly and clearly. The list of selected and integrated policy goals is attached in the Annex and the described tables for the scenario in the Annex. The next chapter presents the results.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Scenario scope

The policy portfolio scenarios are determined by the policy goals identified. Aligned to this the time scope is up to the year 2050. Following the outcomes of the analysis of the focus countries (see **Error! Reference source not found. Error! Reference source not found.;Error! Reference source not found.**), the countries Germany, Italy and the Netherlands have been selected for a detailed analysis. During the consultation process concerning scenario names, the decision was to focus on the aim that is achieved. The chosen names for the baseline/reference scenario, is BioTransition, and for the more ambitious scenario, is BioRevolution. For both scenarios the boundary conditions presented in table 2 were considered.

Table 2: Scenario outline for the specific policy portfolio scenarios

Sector specific	BioTransition	BioRevolution
Overarching policy portfolio scenarios based on EU goals	Timeframe: until 2050 Geographical level: Overarching EU relevant for all sectors	Timeframe: Until 2050 Geographical level: Overarching EU relevant for all sectors
Chemical sector	Timeframe: until 2050 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from the Netherlands	Timeframe: until 2050 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from the Netherlands
Construction sector	Timeframe: until 2050 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from Germany	Timeframe: until 2050 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from Germany (+ additional ones from Netherlands/Italy)
Plastic sector	Timeframe: until 2040 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from Germany	Timeframe: until 2050 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from Germany (+additional ones from Netherlands)
Textile sector	Timeframe: until 2040 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from Italy	Timeframe: until 2050 Geographical level: EU sector specific goals and from Italy (+additional ones from Netherlands)

3.2 Screening criteria

For the selection and identification of the policy goals that are integrated in the scenarios the following elaborated screening criteria have been used (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Screening criteria elaborated based on the EU Circular Action Plan and project understanding of a Circular Bio-based economy (CBBE)

The criteria are described as follows:

- Broaden material use, of biogenic materials, residues and wastes: The integration of biogenic raw materials in material flows is increased by the use of primary biomass, sustainable biowastes or other currently declared waste material flows
- Expand circularity instead of linearity: Within a circular economy no waste or disposal exist and every residual product should be a raw material for other processes
- Scale down amount of waste and disposal: Within a circular economy no waste or disposal exist and every residual product should be a raw material for other processes
- Cut down GHG emissions: By reducing the primary raw material usage and by integrating renewable raw materials GHG emissions are reduced
- Lower biodiversity and land use impacts: Due to the usage of less primary raw materials and increase the circularity less impacts to biodiversity and land use are generated
- Raise efficiency of material usage: The aim of a circular economy is close loops of material flows and reduce the necessary raw materials for the production of products.

3.3 Policy goal data gathering - Overview

Based on the field description of the scenarios and the screening criteria, the following overview shows the metrics of two different collection phases and the collected policy goals. The following illustrates the results of the collection based on the template of specific literature references (see chapter 2.4). Figure 3 illustrates the overarching important metrics of the policy goal collection.

Figure 3: Complete portfolio of identified policy goals (a) Policy goals identified in relation to the reference year; (b) Policy goals identified in relation to their geographical characteristic; (c) Policy goals identified in their qualitative or quantitative characteristic; (d) Policy goals identified having impact on the specific part of the value chain

In the selection process 86 policy goals could be identified. From this the majority of the policy goals are implemented or discussed from the year 2018 to the present year 2023 (Number: 81). Aligned to the project focus, the majority of policy goals are identified at the EU level. Additional efforts were undertaken to collect quantitative goals that would support the modelling task.

Further, we find that most goals impact on the three basic parts of the value chain. Primary on production, second comes emphasis on end-of-life, and only a small number of policies and targets focus on consumption. Following the iterative process of setting specific policy goals in the focus of the developed scenarios, further reduction was made along the selection criteria, possibility for model implementation and focus country setting.

Figure 4 below shows the metrics for the policy goals that are integrated in the scenarios.

Figure 4: Portfolio of identified policy goals integrated in the scenarios (a) Policy goals identified in relation to the reference year; (b) Policy goals identified in relation to their geographical characteristic; (c) Policy goals identified in their qualitative or quantitative characteristic; (d) Policy goals identified having impact on the specific part of the value chain

In the reduction process, about 59 policy goals are retained. The policy goals are implemented or discussed from the year 2017 to the present year 2023. Aligned to the project focus, the majority of policy goals are identified at the EU level, while second most in the Netherlands followed by Italy and Germany. The majority of goals carry a quantitative goal target. Also, in this case, we find that most policies focus on production, followed by end of life and finally consumption.

Additionally, further goals are added via the expert consultations during the INSPIRE Conference. Specifically, 14 additional policy goals are included in the two scenarios, which leads to a final input of policy goals for the scenario generation of 73, that have been used to elaborate the storyline as well as the portfolios of policy goals. A more detailed overview over each collected policy goals is given in the **Error! Reference source not found.** (A3 List of selected and integrated policy goals) in form of small factsheets, along the categories of the template developed.

4 BIOTRANSITION AND BIOEVOLUTION SCENARIO

The following chapters provide insight into the different scenarios, informed by the policy goals and stakeholder inputs gathered throughout the process. This is first done from an overarching point of view, and then at EU and sectoral level for selected countries (see **Error! Reference source not found. Error! Reference source not found.;Error! Reference source not found.**). Each of these chapters starts with an overview of the screening criteria addressed by the policy goals in the status quo followed by the storyline. The table with the specific policy goals aligned to the specific yearly date in each scenario could be found in the **Error! Reference source not found. Table A4 3 - Error! Reference source not found.**.

4.1 Overarching scenario storyline

4.1.1 BioTransition: Transition to a biobased economy

The BioTransition scenario emphasises transition aspects and status quo policy objectives. Transitions are multi-dimensional processes that are characterised by a far-reaching structural change in different regimes of technological, material, economic or political elements (17). It is used in the context of changing aspects in sub-systems (18). The circular economy is one concept that supports the connection of overarching, more holistic frameworks, such as for instance the “bioeconomy”, with focus on the production side and specific use of specific resources. In the BioTransition scenario, this structural change is based on policy goals that address and support aspects of the circular biobased economy concepts and their general system integration. More specifically, quantified goals that focus on altering material flows, waste streams and end-of-life options are considered. In general, this is a prerequisite for a functional circular economy, as it is easier to circulate homogeneous material streams than heterogeneous ones. Within this scenario, the foundations for a circular economy will be laid, but without additional effort to accelerate the transition into a CBBE in terms of speed and scope.

4.1.2 BioRevolution: Revolution to a biobased economy

The BioRevolution scenario includes new and more ambitious goals, aiming at a rapid transformation towards a fully circular bio-based economy. The word of “Revolution” indicates, in our understanding, a more accelerated transformation, that addresses large-scale societal change on several different dimensions (18). Thereby state of the art, forward looking policies are considered that go beyond waste separation and propose more holistic approaches that imply a deeper systemic shift, from linear-oriented systems to more circular ones. This connects this storyline further to the new circular economy action plan (14), which sets a specific focus on the reform of EU waste legislation for example: “ (...) proposes actions along the entire life cycle of products. It targets how products are designed, promotes circular and clean economy processes, encourages sustainable consumption, and announces a review of EU waste legislation with a focus on waste prevention.” (19). Following this storyline, the whole value chain, from resource sourcing to consumption is addressed by the collected policies. Based on adapted time scales for implementation of policy goals, adapting quotas to more ambitious ones or setting voluntary aspects as mandatory for more actors, the circularity of the material flows is increased. In comparison to the status quo of policies, this supports a future pathway where a more ambitious,

faster and holistic transformation towards a fully circular bio-based economy takes place. By increasing policy ambition, the effort to transform the economy to the CBBE is backed up by political support, and the positive impacts of circular material flows for climate mitigation emerge more strongly.

4.2 Overarching portfolio scenarios based on EU goals

In the policy portfolio scenarios, two different levels are considered. Firstly, the overarching policies, which are not explicit for one sector, but are common to all sectors under consideration. These scenarios set the overall boundary conditions for the sectoral policy portfolio scenarios. The second level relates to sector-specific policy goals.

Figure 5: Screening criteria that correspond with identified policy goals of the overarching policy goals on EU level

4.2.1 BioTransition: Transition to a biobased economy

In the overarching storyline of the scenario, 3 different areas could be identified as leading, in line with the identified policy goals. The first area is energy efficiency related aspects (corresponding with screening criteria “Raise efficiency (of material usage)”). Although material flows are considered, circular bio-based concepts must also focus on energy efficiency aspects to gain further advantages over linear fossil-based concepts, and to support the transition to a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy (20) oriented towards the goal of no net emissions (21). The second area focuses on the reduction of waste streams at different levels, but with a focus on municipal wastes (e.g. reduction >55% by 2025 and >60% by 2035) (22, 23). Municipal waste is defined as following: “2b. ‘municipal waste’ means: (a) mixed waste and separately collected waste from households, including paper and cardboard, glass, metals, plastics, biowaste, wood, textiles, packaging, waste electrical and electronic equipment, waste

batteries and accumulators, and bulky waste, including mattresses and furniture; (b) mixed waste and separately collected waste from other sources, where such waste is similar in nature and composition to waste from households;" (23). For the focus sectors expressed, this includes the categories of plastics, biowaste, wood, textile, packaging, (...) and furniture. The third area covers aspects of Greenhouse gas emissions (GHG), net reduction (24) of specific climate gases such as CO₂ (25) (e.g. 55% by 2030), as well as curbing further environmental impacts (22) of material and energetic flows (e.g. reduction of final energy consumption 36% by 2030, renewable energy of 42,5%). The aim is to reduce carbon dependency, recycle carbon from waste streams to replace fossil-based carbons (carbon farming 42 Mio.t contribute to 310 Mio.t LULUCF target), and upscale carbon removal solutions, such as increasing wood products (26), to meet the urgency of climate action (25). These approaches should support the overarching reduction on non-renewable resources and strengthening European economic competitiveness (1) and the adaption of production processes aligned to the planetary boundaries (e.g. decouple economic growth from resource use; reducing dependency on non-renewable unsustainable raw materials) (22). For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 3.

4.2.2 BioRevolution: Revolution to a biobased economy

In the BioRevolution scenario, the identified and selected goals in the BioTransition scenario are adapted. In this scenario the push of CBBE should be envisaged as being more systemic, establishing specific goals also in the material sector. By addressing the importance of connecting the material flows with the overall transformation into a circular biobased economy, it is possible to generate knowledge about the necessary actions that are required in order to accelerate the transformation to a sustainable system. A central aim of the circular biobased economy is to reduce material use and increase efficiency to establish absolute decoupling of resource use from economic growth (21, 27). This supports also the policy goals that addresses the issue of total raw material productivity (see BioRevolution Plastics and Construction), enables the overall more intensive use of secondary raw materials or the integration of more sustainable biobased alternatives, that are part of natural CO₂ circle (see Construction sector: BioRevolution). A further goal is the integration of renewable raw materials to substitute fossil or non-renewable resources (e.g. increase of wood-based products in the global market to 1,5%). For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 4.

4.3 Chemical sector

The chemical sector is an upstream producer for several other sectors, such as for instance construction, textile and plastics. This characteristic differentiates it from the other downstream sectors. As the sector is not the main producer of the final products, end of life policy goals such as separation of waste streams during collection are not directly applicable.

Figure 6: Screening criteria that correspond with identified policy goals of the chemical scenario

4.3.1 BioTransition: Transition to a biobased economy

In the BioTransition scenario, the major leading goal for the chemical sector is the European Communique with its aim of integrating 20% carbon from non-fossil resources by 2030. Besides the reduction of fossil carbon in all systems, the aim is to rethink the sourcing of carbon as a feedstock for industrial production systems. This is supported by e.g. the goal to capture between 300 Mt up to 500 Mt of carbon (25). Another overarching objective is to ensure toxic-free material flows to support the development of circular material flows as well as reduce negative environmental impacts (28). While this aspect also focuses on the waste stream separation and improvement, it fits to the overarching storyline of BioTransition scenario. The policy goals correspond directly with selection criteria “Broaden material use of biogenic materials, residues and wastes” and “Expand circularity instead of linearity”. In the BioTransition scenario, the focus is on the substitution of products through biobased alternatives. Long term goals, such as a toxic free environment, are only less specific or connected to overarching goal systems. In the policy framework, important aspects such as reducing waste disposal or expanding circularity instead of linearity are not set in place.

Country specific aspects: The selected country for the chemical sector is the Netherlands. For the Netherlands, no other specific sectoral policy goals that address the issue of a circular biobased economy could be identified in the research. While no specific policy goals are identified, overarching goals integrated that influence the sector and are having a major impact. Within the latest National Circular Economy Programm (29) several quantitative goals have been raised that

will support the circular economy (e.g. consumption of primary raw material is reduced by 50% by 2030). The most important one for the chemical sector is the reduction of raw material footprint coupled with the reduction of environmental impact. The goal of reduction of 50% primary raw material usage, further addresses these issues (30). For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 5.

4.3.2 BioRevolution: Revolution to a biobased economy

In the BioRevolution scenario, the central scenario assumption for more ambitious policy goals is the increased integration of carbons from non-fossil resources and the earlier implementation of the zero-pollution goal. The biomass use in a circular biobased economy, is a central topic, and changes the resource utilisation of industrial processes more fundamental than for instance adapting to renewable energies. This is underlined if these goals are connected to the already quite ambitious goals of the reduction of primary resource use. In the BioRevolution scenario, the adoption of these practices will reduce the dependency on fossil resources as well as the pollution to the environment. The assumption for raising the quota for integration of carbons from non-fossil resources is adapted from (31). In the meta-analysis several scenario studies indicate that a higher usage of biomass is possible. Along this the quote for biomass usage as feedstock in 2030 is increased to 30% (average value in the scenario studies) and in 2050 40% (focus on the higher values of the scenario studies). It is necessary to consider potential side effects and the type of biomass that is used in the sector. Especially the trade-offs across all bioeconomy sectors need to be considered, such as in this case potential impacts on the EU's carbon sinks (1). The scenario contributes to a feedstock change in the chemical industry, increase the valorization of EU biomasses along the criteria of other strategies (e.g. EU Biodiversity Strategy (32)) and address the challenge of concurrency to other feedstocks if also other sectors of the industry will be de-fossilised.

The pollution from several chemicals and components have a major impact on environmental quality and biodiversity reduction in general (32). Addressing the challenges of End-of-life options the “Chemical strategy for Sustainability” (28) sets further aims to reduce the environmental impacts of these substances. In connection with a higher utilisation of biomass use in the chemical sector, see above, new product development leads to reduced impacts on the environment from an earlier point in time. In the more ambitious scenario, the 0% pollution goal (28), is reached in 2045 and the goal of reduction of substances of concern in recycled materials by 2040. For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 6.

4.4 Construction sector

The construction sector is one of the most material intensive sectors that has the potential to integrate more biobased materials. Especially the use of wood-based construction parts could have several impacts to the raw material usage of the sector.

Figure 7: Screening criteria that correspond with identified policy goals of the construction sector

4.4.1 BioTransition: Transition to a biobased economy

In the BioTransition scenario, the market share of wood-based products is quite low, in comparison to non-metallic raw materials (26). An increase of wood-based products in the market could have several positive impacts for an increase of circularity by adapting the life cycle phases of buildings from construction to renovation and finally deconstruction (26). A major advantage could be seen also in the carbon sequestration that connect the construction sector with the carbon farming initiatives (25). These aspects are matching the criteria of “Broaden material use of biogenic materials, residues and wastes”, and “Cut down GHG emissions”. The most policy goals are on energy related aspects as renovation quotas for the building stock itself (20, 33) (e.g. At least 2% of annual energy renovation by 2030; residential and non-residential buildings, decarbonised building stock by 2050). Based on the status quo of implemented policies, the focus is on separation of material streams in the end of life status (“Scale down waste and disposal”) and to establish a secondary raw material source for further usage (“Expand circularity instead of linearity”) (e.g. 70% by weight from 2020 prepared for recycling or other material recovery). This should additional contribute to overall GHG-emissions reduction.

Country specific aspects: The focus country for the construction sector is Germany. The goal of supporting innovations within the construction of wood-based buildings (34) and integration of other types of wood is qualitatively named. The most important quantitative goal is the total raw material productivity (increase of 1,5%/a), which is embedded in the third resource efficiency

program (35). This corresponds to the criteria of “Raise efficiency of material usage”. These country specific aspects focus on the productivity of the raw materials themselves, less on land use impact issues or boundary conditions. The goal of greater resource efficiency and resource substitution embeds the principle of the circular or closed-loop economy in production processes, and also for the chemical sector (35). For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 7.

4.4.2 BioRevolution: Revolution to a biobased economy

In the BioRevolution scenario, the market share of wood-based products is raised, aligned to the assumptions for a future worldwide market (26). In this case, it is highlighted that trade-offs have to be considered; these arise with the amount of wood needed for an increase of wood-based products in the worldwide market from 1% to 1,5%. The rise of the quota is possible to generate from EU resources, although with possibly high impacts to the competing uses of roundwood (1). In the BioRevolution scenario, the transformation to a circular bio-based economy is not sub-system specific, but cross-cutting. This means that major parts of the industry are integrated, which leads to the assumption that an increase of 0,5% of the assumed worldwide market is realistic. These assumptions are made for the year 2050, but the transformation needs to be supported by further policy goals.

An additional component in the BioRevolution scenario is the change of the EU Taxonomy goals from more or less voluntary to implemented specific goals. This assumes that for reaching a circular biobased economy and transforming the construction sector from a carbon source into a sink, several financial capabilities are necessary. Thus, the EU Taxonomy rules will be implemented as a directive from the year 2030 on. Mandatory product passports could support the monitoring for the implementation of the EU Taxonomy goals. Additionally, the sustainable carbon cycle goal is further explicitly integrated for the construction sector (25) to support the increased deployment of bio-based materials in the sector. If included in the regulations, vacancy management of buildings to maintain old buildings for prolonged usage, could be accounted for further carbon storage conservation. For a long-term, the policy goal in 2025 is implemented to increase further specific capacity building activities for the professionals, that supports the increase in the use of biobased materials

Country specific aspects: The focus country for the construction sector is Germany. At the geographical level, qualitative policy objectives relating to the promotion of innovation in the construction of wood-based buildings (34) and integration of other types of wood. The most important quantitative goal is the overarching one of the total raw material productivity. In the BioRevolution scenario the goal is raised from 1,5% to about 2% (35). This is based on two facts. In the time period 2010 - 2018, the previous goal of 1,5% was not reached and it could be reached through the introduction of higher recycling quotas and increased support of lightweight constructions (36). Therefore, an increase of this quota supports the reaching of the actual policy goal in 2030 and increases the ambition in all sectors. Similar to the Netherlands’ goals of (i) reducing the usage of abiotic materials until 2030 and (ii) integrating as many sustainable renewable raw materials in products, these goals have to be reviewed for their consistency in regard to the EU Taxonomy goals. For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 8.

4.5 Plastic sector

The plastics sector, more than any other, has the most specific policy goals based on EU regulation and at national level. It is a key sector for CBBE transformation due to its high dependency on fossil fuel feedstocks. Therefore, circular biobased concepts could strongly support the transformation of the sector and would have a high impact on the development of a circular biobased economy.

Figure 8: Screening criteria that correspond with identified policy goals of the plastic sector

4.5.1 BioTransition: Transition to a biobased economy

The storyline of the BioTransition scenario is focused on the aspects of reducing waste streams, containing plastics, by recycling (37), ban of products (38) as well as the integration of recycled contents in the material flows (39). These policies are aiming especially on the reduction of waste material flows in general and on negative environmental impacts in particular. Further regulations address the negative influence on human health and ecosystems, by regulating specific ingredients of the products (39) (e.g. lower the sum of concentration levels of lead, cadmium, mercury and hexavalent chromium). Besides the specific and implemented policy goals, a major driver for the alteration of material flows could be the EU Taxonomy, which is voluntary. The Taxonomy sets goals for recycled content in products (e.g. at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material by 2028), the introduction of biobased feedstocks (e.g. use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock by 2028) as well as the overall decrease of per capita reduction of packaging wastes ((a) 5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040) (40). Nevertheless, in the status quo, the uptake of this Taxonomy is limited with regard to the companies that are taking part. In a first FAQ the outreach is quantified between 1-5% (41) . In the BioTransition scenario

these values will be integrated as measurement, although it is assumed that, with a wider implementation of the Green Deal, the quota will increase (21). With this, the selection criteria of “Scale down amount of waste and disposal”; “Expand circularity instead of linearity”; “Broaden material use of biogenic materials, residues and wastes”; “Raise efficiency of material usage” and “Lower biodiversity and land use impacts” are matching. The portfolio of policies in this sector already have an impact on several parts of the value chain from production over consumption to end of life aspects.

Country specific aspects: The focus country for the plastic sector is Germany. Similar to the construction sector, the most important quantitative goal is the total raw material productivity (increase of 1,5%/a), and is an overarching one (35). Additionally, recycling quotas are established to accomplish the legislative quotas (3,8% by 2025; 8,8% by 2030), set in place by the EU (37). In this sector, it is highlighted that the EU level has a high impact on the transition of the sector, while on the selected country level, the focus is still on separation of waste streams and increase of recycling. For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 9.

4.5.2 BioRevolution: Revolution to a biobased economy

In the BioRevolution scenario, further specification of recycling quotas, integration of more plastic categories and mandatory requirements for the production process, especially on the design status, are made. As a result, certain quotas will be increased and bio-based feedstocks will be more widely used in the value chain, for reducing the dependency on fossil resources. Therefore, the policy goal of aligning the production of plastic products, along the design for recycling principles is already set in place in the year 2025 (39). This leads to the earlier and better recyclability of products, reduction of negative environmental impacts as well as the increase of opportunities for circular material flows (14). The policy goal of the EU Taxonomy that ensures that economic activity qualifies as contributing substantially to the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, to the transition to a circular economy (...) (40), sets the goal for 65% of the packaging product by weight consists from sustainable bio-waste feedstock. This is also implemented in this scenario, but not as voluntary as it is in the BioTransition scenario, rather as mandatory. In comparison to the non-mandatory status quo of EU Taxonomy (41), the assumption is that the participation rate among businesses increases significantly.

Country specific aspects: The focus country for the plastic sector is Germany. Similar to the construction sector, the main driving element on the policy level is the quota for total raw material productivity (35). In the BioRevolution scenario, the goal is raised from 1,5% to about 2% (35). This is based on two facts. Firstly, in the time period 2010 - 2018, the previous goal of 1,5% was not reached (36) and secondly higher recycling quotas supports to reach the policy goal for total raw material productivity in 2030. Additionally, this supports reaching the aim of the EU legislative for recycled plastic (37). The increase of total raw material productivity is further supported by the implementation of per capita policy goals for the reduction of packaging waste (39). This is in line with the policy goal of the Netherlands (Annual reduction in growth of plastic: 1,5 %/a (42)). Thus, a quota should be implemented from the year 2025 on, and raises the proposed quota for 2030 to 7,5% and extend the goal from only packaging waste to general growth reduction. In general, these two policy objectives in the BioRevolution scenario address the problem of increasing plastic waste streams in the last years (43). The BioRevolution scenario illustrates that, in the plastic sector,

both the production level and the consumption level have to be integrated much stronger. In addition to the focus on the overall reduction in growth of plastic, other sectors besides packaging should be evaluated and alternatives are used, such as less use of plastics in the agricultural sector.

At the country level the recycling quota for several materials are already achieved (e.g. recycling goal for wood (2030: 30%)). In the year 2021, it was already at 48,4% for plastics (43). This leads to the assumption that the recycling goal from the EU for plastics (2025: 50%; 2030: 55%) will be reached. To accelerate the transformation to a CBBE for the year 2030, an increase of 5% is assumed, leading to the new goal of 60% in 2030 for plastics and 35% for wood packaging. Next to these policy goals, the circular material flows increase due the wider implementation and usage of chemical recycling techniques. While the Netherlands raised the goal for mechanical recycling to 50%, and for chemical recycling to 10% until 2030 (42), further assumptions show that raising the mechanical recycling to 40% and the chemical recycling to 20% until 2050 would majorly support the transition to a future CBBE (27). Following these both ranges, in the scenario for the year 2040, the aim is to reach a mechanical recycling quota for plastics of 45% and for chemical recycling of plastics of 15%. For the year 2050, finally the fossil-based production should be phased out as much as possible and plastic production is based on recycled plastic, substitution of biobased materials or based on CCU applications. For this end-point, it is necessary to consider the limitation concerning the amount of plastics that is actually used and available for recycling, given the reduction assumed in the BioRevolution scenario. For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found. Error! Reference source not found.**

4.6 Textile sector

The Textile sector is, in comparison to other policies, characterised by an earlier stage of policy goal implementation to increase the share of circular material flows. In the latest policy framework in the sector the issue of the imports to Europe is raised. As the EU is one of the major consumer of textiles, it is necessary to accomplish a higher circularity of textile material flows, to reduce the overall textile consumption that increases waste stream problems as well as negative environmental impacts (48).

Figure 9: Screening criteria that correspond with identified policy goals of the textile sector

4.6.1 BioTransition: Transition to a biobased economy

The BioTransition sector concentrates on the separate collection and reuse of textiles at the point of disposal (23, 45). The latest strategy of the EU addresses several aspects that should be focused on, such as an increase of recycled fibers within the products, absence of hazardous substances and production processes in respect of social rights and the environment until the year 2030 (47). Thereby the key actions are seen in the topics of comprehensible eco-design requirements, stopping the destruction of unsold and unused fabrics, tackling microplastic pollution (in connection to the Zero Pollution Action Plan (22)), information requirements for the customer, green claims and extended producer responsibility schemes. Addressing these issues is connected with monitoring of material flows. This means that in the first place the separate collection of textiles in waste streams needs to be established on a wider scale (23).

Country specific aspects: The focus country for the textile sector is Italy. As a central country for the textile industry, already policy goals are in place, with the aim of 100% recovery in the textile industry (45). The more overarching framework of the Italian National Circular Economy Strategy (46), supports this by focusing on the introduction of a fiscal system favourable for a secondary market. Additional upstream circularity strategies are planned, such as eco-design requirements and extending the lifespan of products and parts (47). As these goals are more qualitative in nature, the focus in the BioTransition scenario will be to introduce a 100% recovery of textiles by 2026 and reduce the annual energy consumption of the non-ETS sector (48). For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found.** Table A4 11.

4.6.2 BioRevolution: Revolution to a biobased economy

In the BioRevolution scenario the goals of the EU Textile strategy are implemented and additional recycling targets are addressed. For the specific case of clothing the new or additional policy goals are oriented along the National Circular Economy Strategy of the Netherlands that integrates specific quantitative goals (29). These goals are addressing more in detail the aims out of the EU Textile strategy (44). As these goals are country specific, the adoption at EU level would probably take more time for the implementation. Thus, the first policy goals will be put in the scenario in place about 2,5 years later and correspond more strongly with the Italian national goal of 100 % recovery in “Textile Hubs” (45). After this later implementation, other goals for 2030 are implemented in 2030, as the fundamentals for a more circular economy (e.g. separation of waste streams, recycling quotas) is established and experiences from other sectors (e.g. Plastic) could be used to adapt material flows in a more circular way.

Additionally, other specific support for organisations that support local or regional infrastructures to enable a higher rate of sharing textiles. Following results of the JRC (49), a higher reuse rate would have several positive impacts to life cycle categories such as climate change, urban land occupation or natural land transformation. This goal would directly address the consumption side and could be implemented on short notice. Further this connects quite well to the approach of “Textile Hubs”. Another goal for addressing the end of life status of textiles is the obligation to fully recycle, reuse or refurbish unsold textiles. This reduces the consumption of new textiles and prevents the waste of raw materials. Along with the restriction to use more recycled clothes, this could be also supportive for the other goals in 2030.

In the BioRevolution scenario, further aspects are integrated that address also the production processes of textile. In the year 2030, the wool production should be qualified and sourced from regenerative agricultural practices. This addresses additionally to the reuse and sharing economy the impacts of natural land transformation and land occupation and could be used to reach the goal in 2050 that incentives bio-based materials in the value chain. In relation to this full product delivery chain perspective, a carbon tax implemented for all fashion products would further increase the reuse of textiles and could be a favourable fiscal policy to support a secondary market establishment in the year 2035 (47). For the detailed overview of included policies sorted by the respective focus year see **Error! Reference source not found. Error! Reference source not found.**

5 CONCLUSION

This report presents the results of the work carried out in the SUSTRACK Task 4.1. The task focused on the review of existing policy goals, the development of portfolio policy scenarios, and the identification of more ambitious policy goals for accelerating and intensifying the transformation into a circular biobased economy. 49 policy documents have been extensively reviewed for the identification of policy goals relevant to the development of a circular biobased economy. The review explicitly focused on policy goals that include qualitative and quantitative information from a macro level perspective. This informs the choice of measures to be included in GEM, with processable data for scenario analysis and impact assessment. Additionally, the case study work is contextualised. The review and scenario formulation have provided the following main outputs for the SUSTRACK project.

First, 86 policy goals at the EU as well as at country level have been identified as being relevant for a circular biobased economy, and about 59 of these were integrated in the scenarios. We found it necessary to establish an overall framework with screening criteria (see chapter 2.3) to select the appropriate policy goals for the illustration of a present and future ambition for a circular biobased economy. Following this approach, an extensive portfolio of policy goals that have impact to the circular economy was compiled. This not only informs the upcoming modelling task, but also provides a compendium of policies (especially quantitative ones) that support the discussion about policy frameworks for the four project sectors.

Second, it becomes clear that policy elaboration and further development of policy goals depend on several aspects. This could not be easily assumed by sectoral practitioners or stakeholders in a conference workshop, besides many other topics. The knowledge of experts as well as literature review are more favourable for this in the first place. A further discussion about the goals as well as the implementation options seems more convenient within a specific, explicit setting. The more ambitious (BioRevolution) scenario addresses several aspects, also mentioned by stakeholders, in a more general manner, and places them in some context that the policy goals are useful for the modelling task.

Third, the policy portfolio scenarios give insights into the different sectors that are central for a transformation into a circular biobased economy.

The policy portfolio scenarios at the overarching EU level highlight the importance of reducing material use while increasing efficiency as a key factor in decoupling resource use from economic growth in absolute terms. The circular biobased economy establishes thereby an opportunity to reduce dependencies on non-renewable, unsustainable resources and supports the creation of a toxic-free environment.

In the chemicals sector they illustrate higher shares of non-fossil-based carbon in material flows as a major goal. This supports achieving the zero-pollution target earlier, the reduction of substances of concern in recycled materials and reaching overarching EU level goals.

For the construction sector they emphasise that a higher share of biobased products assist the transformation from a carbon source to a carbon sink. The increase of total raw material productivity and use of secondary materials aims to increase circularity of material flows and reduce the overall dependency on non-abiotic resources.

In the plastic sector, the already implemented policy goals encourage an increase of ambition and showcase the importance of the sector for the circular economy. A faster implementation of a feedstock change for the production, further specification of recycling quotas and content quotas for integration of non-fossil based materials could be a blueprint for other sectors and guide the way into a circular biobased economy.

For the textile sector, the focus on the separation of waste streams increases the resource efficiency by reducing waste and disposal streams. Additional quantitative goals for the integration of recycled products and sustainable textiles in the value chains support the transformation in the sector.

The policy portfolio scenarios illustrate the importance of governance structures that build the framework for a faster and holistic transformation of material flows in Europe. The circular biobased economy is decisive in achieving climate goals and adaptation of the whole system in a more sustainable way, with the focus on circularity, decoupling of resource use from economic growth and the reduction of negative environmental impacts.

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Project Consortium

ANNEX

Table A1 1: Selection criteria for countries and interpretation (Economic)

Sectors	Selection criteria for countries and interpretation	Sources
Chemicals	Germany and France are the two largest chemicals producers in Europe valued at €274.7 billion, followed by Italy and the Netherlands. These four countries accounted for 66.2% of EU27 chemical sales in 2021, valued at €393.0 billion. The share rose to 84.3%, or €500.3 billion, when including Spain, Belgium, and Austria. The remaining 20 Member States of the EU accounted for 15.7% of EU27 chemical sales in 2021, with Sweden and Poland being the biggest among them.	(64)
Construction	Annual production value of the construction industry in selected European countries 2020 In billion EUR Top 6: Germany (360,27); France (318,93); Italy (168,2); Spain (140,56); Poland (91,01); Netherlands (85,42)	(65)
Plastics	Plastics converted demand Top 5: Germany, Italy, France, Spain, Poland and for Consumption and Production Top 5: Germany, France, Spain, Netherlands, Belgium	(66, 67)
Textile	The biggest producers in the industry are Italy, France, Germany, Spain and Portugal. Together, they account for about three-quarters of EU production.	(68, 69)

Table A1 2: Selection criteria for countries and interpretation (Emissions)

Description of criteria	GHG-Emission	Sources
Total country GHG emissions in 2019	The top-countries are following: 1. Germany; 2. France; 3. Italy; 4. Poland; 5. Spain; 6. Netherlands; 7. Czech Republic; 8. Belgium	(70)
Chemical sector GHG emissions in 2019 (including plastics)	The top-countries are following: 1. Belgium; 2. France; 3. Netherlands; 4. Germany; 5. Poland	(70)
Manufacturing industries and construction sector GHG emissions in 2019	The top-countries are following: 1. Germany; 2. Italy; 3. France; 4. Spain; 5. Poland; 6. Netherlands	(70)

D4.1. Report presenting scenarios and related policy packages

Figure A2 1: Input collected for the plastic sector in the INSPIRE conference

<p>TASKS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add existing policy goals in the sector. 2. Add additional new policy goals in the sector. 	<p>GLOSSARY</p> <p>Policy goals: Desired future conditions/state to be achieved, ideally in quantitative terms.</p> <p>Policy selection criteria Circular bio-based economy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expand circularity instead linearity Broaden material use of biogenic materials, residues and wastes (phase out fossil) Raise efficiency (of material usage) Lower biodiversity and land use impacts Scale down amount of waste and disposal Cut down GHG emissions <p>Existing policy goals: Existing policy goals based on regulations, directives, strategy documents, NDC plans or others. Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> implemented or under discussion sectoral or overarching goals (green notes with red tag) and sector specific goals (green notes without red tag) <p>Additional new policy goals: Additional new policy goals, which support a faster and more efficient transition towards CBBE. Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on existing policy goals (e.g. reaching earlier or a higher/lower goals) completely new goals 	<p>INSPIRE policy scenario workshop - Plastic</p>	<p>Existing policy goals </p> <p>Additional new policy goals </p>
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D4.1. Report presenting scenarios and related policy packages

Figure A2 2: Input collected for the chemicals sector in the INSPIRE conference

<p>TASKS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add existing policy goals in the sector. 2. Add additional new policy goals in the sector. 	<p>GLOSSARY</p> <p>Policy goals: Desired future conditions/state to be achieved, ideally in quantitative terms.</p> <p>Policy selection criteria Circular bio-based economy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand circularity instead linearity • Broaden material use of biogenic materials, residues and wastes (phase out fossil) • Raise efficiency (of material usage) • Lower biodiversity and land use impacts • Scale down amount of waste and disposal • Cut down GHG emissions <p>Existing policy goals: Existing policy goals based on regulations, directives, strategy documents, NDC plans or others. Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implemented or under discussion • sectoral or overarching goals (green notes with red tag) and sector specific goals (green notes without red tag) <p>Additional new policy goals: Additional new policy goals, which support a faster and more efficient transition towards CBBE.</p> <p>Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on existing policy goals (e.g. reaching earlier or a higher/lower goals) • completely new goals 	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>INSPIRE policy scenario workshop - Chemicals</p> </div>	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Existing policy goals </p> <p>Additional new policy goals </p> </div>
	<p>EU </p>	<p>COUNTRY SPECIFIC</p> <p> ITA NL GER</p> <p> OTHERS</p>	

D4.1. Report presenting scenarios and related policy packages

Figure A2 3: Input collected for the textile sector in the INSPIRE conference

TASKS	GLOSSARY	EU	COUNTRY SPECIFIC	INSPIRE CONFERENCE INSPIRE policy scenario workshop - Textile	Legend
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add existing policy goals in the sector. 2. Add additional new policy goals in the sector. 	<p>Policy goals: Describes a range of desired outcomes <-> not measures or instruments that are used to reach the policy goals</p> <p>Policy selection criteria Circular bio-based economy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expand circularity instead linearity Broaden material use of biogenic materials, residues and wastes (phase out fossil) Raise efficiency (of material usage) Lower biodiversity and land use impacts Scale down amount of waste and disposal Cut down GHG emissions <p>Existing policy goals: Existing policy goals based on regulations, directives, strategy documents, NDC plans or others. Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> implemented or under discussion sectoral or overarching goals (green notes with red tag) and sector specific goals (green notes without red tag) <p>Additional new policy goals: Additional new policy goals, which support a faster and more efficient transition towards CBBE. Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on existing policy goals (e.g. reaching earlier or a higher/lower goals) completely new goals 	</p>			

D4.1. Report presenting scenarios and related policy packages

Figure A2 4: Input collected for the construction sector in the INSPIRE conference

<p>TASKS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add existing policy goals in the sector. 2. Add additional new policy goals in the sector. 	<p>GLOSSARY</p> <p>Policy goals: Desired future conditions/state to be achieved, ideally in quantitative terms.</p> <p>Policy selection criteria Circular bio-based economy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand circularity instead linearity • Broaden material use of biogenic materials, residues and wastes (phase out fossil) • Raise efficiency (of material usage) • Lower biodiversity and land use impacts • Scale down amount of waste and disposal • Cut down GHG emissions <p>Existing policy goals: Existing policy goals based on regulations, directives, strategy documents, NDC plans or others. Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implemented or under discussion • sectoral or overarching goals (green notes with red tag) and sector specific goals (green notes without red tag) <p>Additional new policy goals: Additional new policy goals, which support a faster and more efficient transition towards CBBE. Possibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on existing policy goals (e.g. reaching earlier or a higher/lower goals) • completely new goals 	<div style="text-align: center;">
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A3 List of selected and integrated policy goals

A3.1 EU Overarching goals

Policy document name	The European Green Deal (21)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	No net emission of greenhouse gas emissions in EU by 2050 where economic growth is decoupled from resource use.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	(...) aims to transform the EU into a fair and prosperous society, with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy where there are no net emissions of greenhouse gases in 2050 and where economic growth is decoupled from resource use. (...) aims to protect, conserve and enhance the EU's natural capital, and protect the health and well-being of citizens from environment-related risks and impacts. At the same time, this transition must be just and inclusive.
Year specified	1	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	New EU Forest Strategy for 2030 (26)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals.

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Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	The Commission will develop a 2050 roadmap for reducing whole life-cycle carbon emissions in buildings. In the context of the revision of the Construction Products Regulation , the Commission will develop a standard, robust and transparent methodology to quantify the climate benefits of wood construction products and other building materials.
Expected Impact	1	(...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink.
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on energy efficiency (recast) (20)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	At least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency by 2030; Reducing primary (39%) and final (36%) energy consumption by 2030
	2	Annual energy savings obligations by MSs: 2024-2030: >1.5%
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Quota
Expected Impact	1	(...) Energy efficiency is a key area of action, without which the full decarbonisation of the Union ´s economy cannot be achieved.
	2	(...) Energy efficiency is a key area of action, without which the full decarbonisation of the Union ´s economy cannot be achieved.
Year specified	1	2030
	2	2030

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Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production

Policy document name	The European Climate Law (24)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Net reduction of GHG emissions by at least 55% (By 2030 vs. 1990 level) (225 million tonnes of CO2 equivalent)
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Law
Expected Impact	1	This Regulation establishes a framework for the irreversible and gradual reduction of anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions by sources and enhancement of removals by sinks regulated in Union law
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Renewable Energy Directive (27)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) Overall Union renewable energy target to 42,5 % in the energy mix

Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Binding goal
Expected Impact	1	Reaching intermediate target of a reduction of net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55 % compared to 1990 levels by 2030
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (23)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Increasing municipal waste recycling: >55% by weight by 2025 >60% by weight by 2035
	2	Article 8a (4c(i)) in the case of extended producer responsibility schemes established to attain waste management targets and objectives established under legislative acts of the Union, the producers of products bear at least 80 % of the necessary costs (...)
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	1	Quota/Cost sharing/Information
Expected Impact	1	Reduction of municipal wastes
	2	Article 8 (1.) (...) strengthen the re-use and the prevention, recycling and other recovery of waste (...)
Year specified	1	2025/2035

	2	80 % when implemented after 4. July 2018 50% when implemented before 4. July 2018
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	Production

Policy document name	COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 1999/31/EC of 26 April 1999 on the landfill of waste (28)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Restrict landfilling of waste recyclable or suitable for energy recovery
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Ban
Expected Impact	1	(...) is to ensure a progressive reduction of landfilling of waste, in particular of waste that is suitable for recycling or other recovery, and, by way of stringent operational and technical requirements on the waste and land fills, to provide for measures, procedures and guidance (...)
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life

Policy document name	A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe - Strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment : updated bioeconomy strategy (1)	
Qualitative		

Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) are managing natural resources sustainably, reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, limiting and adapting to climate change and strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs. (...) 1% increase of European wood-based products in the market share of the global construction, textile and plastics markets could
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	-
Expected Impact	1	generate a revenue for the European wood-based bioeconomy in the scale of EUR 10 to 60 billion. This would amount to 3% - 20% of the current total turnover of the EU forest industry. The additional industrial roundwood use of this 1% increase would be at least 83 million cubic metres, which would be 23% of the total industrial roundwood production in the EU in 2016 (355 million cubic metres, data FAOSTAT).
Year specified	1	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Consumption

Policy document name	Sustainable Carbon Cycles (25)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Carbon farming should contribute -42 Mio. t CO ₂ eq to -310 Mio. t LULUCF target
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Amount
Expected Impact	1	(...) increase carbon sink

Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Pathway to a Healthy Planet for All EU Action Plan: 'Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil' (22)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Air, water and soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with, thus creating a toxic-free environment.
	2	Under EU law, Green Deal ambitions and in synergy with other initiatives, by 2030 the EU should reduce: (...) 6. significantly total waste generation and by 50% residual municipal waste.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Planetary boundaries
	2	Quota
Expected Impact	1	"Air, water and soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with"
	2	Reaching zero pollution targets by 2050
Year specified	1	2050
	2	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	End of life

EU Chemical sector

Policy document name	Sustainable Carbon Cycles (25)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	By 2028, any ton of CO ₂ captured, transported, used and stored by industries should be reported and accounted by its fossil, biogenic or atmospheric origin;
	2	At least 20% of the carbon used in the chemical and plastic products should be from sustainable non-fossil sources by 2030, in full consideration of the EU's biodiversity and circular economy objectives and of the upcoming policy framework for bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics.
	3	5 Mt of CO ₂ should be annually removed from the atmosphere and permanently stored through frontrunner projects by 2030
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Reporting
	2	Quota
	3	Quota
Expected Impact	1	(...)reduce our reliance on carbon
	2	(...) recycle carbon from waste streams, from sustainable sources of biomass or directly from the atmosphere, to use it in place of fossil carbon
	3	(...) we need to upscale carbon removal solutions that capture CO ₂ from the atmosphere and store it for the long term
Year specified	1	2028
	2	2030
	3	2030
	1	Production

Part of the value chain addressed	2	Production
	3	Production

Policy document name	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment (30)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	In a clean circular economy it is essential to boost the production and uptake of secondary raw materials and ensure that both primary and secondary materials and products are always safe. (...)However, the creation of a well-functioning market for secondary raw materials and the transition to safer materials and products is being slowed down by a number of issues, in particular the lack of adequate information on the chemical content of products (...).To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that “Recycled in the EU” becomes a benchmark worldwide , it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimised.(...)
	2	0% pollution for air, water, and soil
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Ban, Assessment
	2	Quota
Expected Impact	1	(...) This includes ensuring that all chemicals are used more safely and sustainably, promoting that chemicals having a chronic effect for human health and the environment - substances of concern - are minimised and substituted as far as possible, and phasing out the most harmful ones for non-essential societal use, in particular in consumer products.(...)
	2	(...) aims to better protect citizens and the environment, and boost innovation for safe and sustainable chemicals, including in construction where chemicals are omnipresent.
Year specified	1	-
	2	2050

Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Consumption

EU Construction sector

Policy document name	A renovation Wave for Europe greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives (35)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	2020: Annual renovation rate for energy renovation about 1% and deep renovation rate cutting 60 % of energy needs is about 0,2 % (Base: Building Stock 85% = 220 Mio. building units) 2030: At least 2% of annual energy renovation (160,000 jobs could be created, foster deep renovation rate); maximum about 35 Mio
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	(...) Communication presents a strategy to trigger a Renovation Wave for Europe, breaking down long-standing barriers to energy and resource-efficient renovation supporting fresh investment over a sustained period starting from public and less efficient buildings, spurring digitalisation and creating employment and growth opportunities across the renovation supply chain
Expected Impact	1	Increase in jobs and material usage
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Consumption

Policy document name	New EU Forest Strategy for 2030 (26)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals.

Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	The Commission will develop a 2050 roadmap for reducing whole life-cycle carbon emissions in buildings. In the context of the revision of the Construction Products Regulation, the Commission will develop a standard, robust and transparent methodology to quantify the climate benefits of wood construction products and other building materials.
Expected Impact	1	(...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink.
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on energy efficiency (recast) (20)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) double their annual energy savings obligations, leading the way by action throughout the public sector. (...) renovate 3% of their buildings' floor space annually.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	The embodied carbon in construction is estimated to account for about 10% of total yearly greenhouse gas emissions worldwide, see IRP, Resource Efficiency and Climate Change, 2020, and UN Environment Emissions Gap Report 2019 (67 p. 37) Increase in material usage
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Directive 2010/31/EE of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings (recast) (40)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Each Member State shall establish a long-term renovation strategy to support the renovation of the national stock of residential and non-residential buildings, both public and private, into a highly energy efficient and decarbonised building stock by 2050, facilitating the cost-effective transformation of existing buildings into nearly zero-energy buildings.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	(...) Set out a roadmap with measures and domestically established measurable progress indicators, with a view to the long-term 2050 (...) The roadmap shall include indicative milestones for 2030, 2040 and 2050, and specify how they contribute to achieving the Union's energy efficiency targets in accordance with Directive 2012/27/EU
Expected Impact	1	(...) reducing greenhouse gas emissions in the Union by 80-95 % compared to 1990, in order to ensure a highly energy efficient and decarbonised national building stock and in order to facilitate the cost-effective transformation of existing buildings into nearly zero-energy buildings
Year specified	1	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (23)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Article 11 (2a) "(...) (b) by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery, including backfilling operations using waste to substitute other materials, of non-hazardous construction and demolition waste excluding naturally occurring material defined in category 17 05 04 in the list of waste shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;"

Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Article 11 (1.) (...) promote preparing for re-use activities, notably by encouraging the establishment of and support for preparing for re-use and repair networks, by facilitating, where compatible with proper waste management, their access to waste held by collection schemes or facilities that can be prepared for re-use but is not destined for preparing for re-use by those schemes or facilities, and by promoting the use of economic instruments, procurement criteria, quantitative objectives or other measures.(...)
Year specified	1	2020
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life

Policy document name	ANNEX to the COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) .../... supplementing Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council by establishing the technical screening criteria for determining the conditions under which an economic activity qualifies as contributing substantially to the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, to the transition to a circular economy, to pollution prevention and control or to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems and for determining whether that economic activity causes no significant harm to any of the other environmental objectives and amending Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2178 as regards specific public disclosures for those economic activities (38)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	<p>4. The use of primary raw material in the construction of the building is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. The operator of the activity ensures that the three heaviest material categories used to construct the building, measured by mass in kilogrammes, comply with the following maximum total amounts of primary raw material used:</p> <p>(a) for the combined total of concrete, natural or agglomerated stone, a maximum of 70% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(b) for the combined total of brick, tile, ceramic, a maximum of 70% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(c) for bio-based materials, a maximum of 80% of the total material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(d) for the combined total of glass, mineral insulation, a maximum of 70% of the total material come from primary raw material;</p>

		<p>(e) for non-biobased plastic, a maximum of 50% of the total material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(f) for metals, a maximum of 30% of the total material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(g) for gypsum, a maximum of 65% of the material come from primary raw material.</p>
	2	<p>5. The use of primary raw material in the renovation of the building is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. The operator of the activity ensures that the three heaviest material categories that have been newly added to the building in the renovation of the building, measured by mass in kilogrammes, comply with the following thresholds regarding the maximum amount of primary raw material used:</p> <p>(a) for the combined total of concrete, natural or agglomerated stone, a maximum of 85% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(b) for the combined total of brick, tile, ceramic, a maximum of 85% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(c) for bio-based materials, a maximum of 90% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(d) for the combined total of glass, mineral insulation, a maximum of 85% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(e) for non-biobased plastic, a maximum of 75% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(f) for metals, a maximum of 65% of the material come from primary raw material;</p> <p>(g) for gypsum, a maximum of 83% of the material come from primary raw material.</p>
	3	<p>4. The preparing for re-use or recycling of the non-hazardous construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90% (by mass in kilogrammes), excluding backfilling. This excludes naturally occurring material referred to in category 17 05 04 in the European List of Waste established by Commission Decision 2000/532/EC.</p> <p>The operator of the activity demonstrates compliance with the 90% threshold by reporting (...). Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled.</p>
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Quota

	3	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Substantial contribution to the transition to a circular economy
	2	Substantial contribution to the transition to a circular economy
	3	Substantial contribution to the transition to a circular economy
Year specified	1	-
	2	-
	3	-
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production
	3	End of life

Policy document name	Expert knowledge without specific policy document reference based on the input of the INSPIRE conference	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	Oblige/stimulate insulation of all rented houses by 2030/2050
	2	Establishment of a (mandatory) Digital Product Passport for construction products on European level with - besides others - information regarding repair, reuse, recycling as well as biomass content.
	3	Buildings renovation quota/targets
	4	Incentives for the deployment of bio-based materials in construction

	5	Vacancy management to maintain old buildings and availability of buildings for prolonged usage
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Regulatory
	2	Regulatory
	3	Quota
	4	Incentives
	5	Incentives
Expected Impact	1	Higher energy efficiency
	2	Consumer information
	3	Increase in energy efficiency
	4	Less fossil resource increase e in bio-based materials
	5	Less vacancies and less primary raw material usage
Year specified	1	2030
	2	2030
	3	2050
	4	2050
	5	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Consumption

	3	Production
	4	Production
	5	Production

EU Plastic sector

Policy document name	Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on packaging and packaging waste, amending Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and Directive (EU) 2019/904, and repealing Directive 94/62/EC (44)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Article 5 (5) (...) lower the sum of concentration levels of lead, cadmium, mercury and hexavalent chromium resulting from substances present in packaging or packaging components (...)
	2	Article 6 (1) All packaging shall be recyclable. Article 6 (3) Recyclable packaging shall, from 1 January 2030, comply with the design for recycling criteria as laid down in the delegated acts adopted pursuant to paragraph 4 and, from 1 January 2035, also with the recyclability at scale requirements laid down in the delegated acts adopted pursuant to paragraph 6.(...)
	3	Article 7 (1) From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component; (b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c)

	<p>2. From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging:</p> <p>(a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b);</p>
4	<p>Article 38 (1) Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, as compared to the packaging waste generated per capita in 2018 as reported to the Commission in accordance with Decision 2005/270/EC, by</p> <p>(a) 5 % by 2030;</p> <p>(b) 10 % by 2035;</p> <p>(c) 15 % by 2040</p>
5	<p>Article 46 (1) Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets covering the whole of their territory:</p> <p>(a) by 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated;</p> <p>(b) by 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated:</p> <p>(i) 50 % of plastic;</p> <p>(ii) 25 % of wood;</p> <p>(iii) 70 % of ferrous metals;</p> <p>(iv) 50 % of aluminium;</p> <p>(v) 70 % of glass;</p> <p>(vi) 75 % of paper and cardboard;</p> <p>(c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated;</p> <p>(d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated:</p> <p>(i) 55 % of plastic;</p> <p>(ii) 30 % of wood;</p> <p>(iii) 80 % of ferrous metals;</p> <p>(iv) 60 % of aluminium;</p> <p>(v) 75 % of glass;</p>

		(vi) 85 % of paper and cardboard
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota/Reference levels
	2	Product specifications
	3	Quota
	4	Quota
	5	Quota
Expected Impact	All	(...) establishes requirements for the entire life cycle of packaging as regards environmental sustainability and labelling, to allow its placing on the market, as well as for the extended producer responsibility, collection, treatment and recycling of packaging waste (...) (...) contributes to the efficient functioning of the internal market by harmonising national measures on packaging and packaging waste in order to avoid obstacles to trade, distortion and restriction of competition within the Union (...)
	1	Article 5 (4) (...) They shall address, as appropriate, substances of concern that negatively affect the re-use and recycling of materials in the packaging in which they are present.(...)
	2	Higher percentage of recyclable packaging products
	3	Increase of raw material efficiency
	4	Waste prevention
	5	Recycling targets and promotion of recycling
Year specified	1	-
	2	2030/2035
	3	2030/2040
	4	2030/2035/2040

	5	2025/2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	Production
	3	Production
	4	End of life
	5	End of life

Policy document name	Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 November 2008 on waste and repealing certain Directives (23)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	"Article 11 (1) " (...) member states shall set up separate collection at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass, and, by 1 January 2025, for textiles""
	2	<p>Article 8a (1.) (...) Member States shall take the necessary measures to ensure that the financial contributions paid by the producer of the product to comply with its extended producer responsibility obligations:</p> <p>(a) cover the following costs for the products that the producer puts on the market in the Member State concerned:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – costs of separate collection of waste and its subsequent transport and treatment, including treatment necessary to meet the Union waste management targets, and costs necessary to meet other targets and objectives as referred to in point (b) of paragraph 1, taking into account the revenues from re-use, from sales of secondary raw material from its products and from unclaimed deposit fees, – costs of providing adequate information to waste holders in accordance with paragraph 2, – costs of data gathering and reporting in accordance with point (c) of paragraph 1.
	1	Separation

Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	2	Cost sharing
Expected Impact	1	“Article 11 (1.) Member States shall take measures to promote preparing for re-use activities, notably by encouraging the establishment of and support for preparing for re-use and repair networks, by facilitating, where compatible with proper waste management, their access to waste held by collection schemes or facilities that can be prepared for re-use but is not destined for preparing for re-use by those schemes or facilities, and by promoting the use of economic instruments, procurement criteria, quantitative objectives or other measures.
	2	“Article 8 (1.) In order to strengthen the re-use and the prevention, recycling and other recovery of waste, Member States may take legislative or non- legislative measures to ensure that any natural or legal person who professionally develops, manufactures, processes, treats, sells or imports products (producer of the product) has extended producer responsibility”
Year specified	1	2025
	2	-
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	End of life

Policy document name	ANNEX to the COMMISSION DELEGATED REGULATION (EU) .../... supplementing Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council by establishing the technical screening criteria for determining the conditions under which an economic activity qualifies as contributing substantially to the sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, to the transition to a circular economy, to pollution prevention and control or to the protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems and for determining whether that economic activity causes no significant harm to any of the other environmental objectives and amending Delegated Regulation (EU) 2021/2178 as regards specific public disclosures for those economic activities (38)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	1. The activity complies with one of the following criteria: (a) use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging.

		<p>From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging;</p> <p>(b) design for reuse: the packaging product has been designed to be reusable within a reuse system and fulfils the requirements for the use of circular feedstock, as set in point 1.a with 35% and 10% targets for recycled feedstock applying as of 2028 and 65% and 50% targets applying as of 2032</p> <p>(a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock*</p> <p>(*Sustainable bio-waste feedstock refers to industrial bio-waste and municipal bio-waste, it excludes primary biomass in the absence of legally agreed sustainability criteria.)</p>
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Substantial contribution to the transition to a circular economy
Year specified	1	2028/2032
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Directive (EU) 2019/ of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (43)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Article 4 (1) Member States shall take the necessary measures to achieve an ambitious and sustained reduction in the consumption of the single-use plastic products listed in Part A of the Annex, in line with the overall objectives of the Union’s waste policy, in particular waste prevention, leading to a substantial reversal of increasing consumption trends. Those measures shall achieve a measurable quantitative reduction in the consumption of the single-use plastic products listed in Part A of the Annex on the territory of the Member State by 2026 compared to 2022

	2	Article 5 Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic.
	3	Article 6 (5) With regard to beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex, each Member State shall ensure that: (a) from 2025, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex which are manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic, calculated as an average for all PET bottles placed on the market on the territory of that Member State; and (b) from 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic, calculated as an average for all such beverage bottles placed on the market on the territory of that Member State.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	No specific
	2	Ban
	3	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Consumption reduction
	2	(...) to prevent and reduce the impact of certain plastic products on the environment, in particular the aquatic environment, and on human health
	3	(...) to promote the transition to a circular economy with innovative and sustainable business models, products and materials, thus also contributing to the efficient functioning of the internal market
Year specified	1	2026
	2	In force
	3	2025/2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Consumption
	2	Consumption
	3	Production

Policy document name	Expert knowledge without specific policy document reference based on the input of the INSPIRE conference	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Less use of plastics in agriculture (mulch films, foil tunnels ect.)
	2	No fossil based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU)
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Ban
	2	Ban
Expected Impact	1	Reduction of negative impacts of fossil fuel use
	2	Reduction of negative impacts of fossil fuel use
Year specified	1	2030
	2	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	End of life

EU Textile sector

Policy document name	EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles (48)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		

Goal qualitative description	1	"establishes the framework for setting ecodesign requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects."
	2	"(...) to support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products"
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Certification
	2	Information
Expected Impact	1	"framework will enable the introduction of product performance and information requirements to be set for almost all categories of physical goods placed on the EU market."
	2	"to support its uptake among producers (...)"
Year specified	1	-
	2	-
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Consumption

Policy document name	Expert knowledge without specific policy document reference based on the input of the INSPIRE conference	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	Fortify local/ regional infrastructures to enable sharing of textiles (or other resources)
	2	Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion (now 30% of fashion in never sold)

	3	supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertilizer)
	4	Increase incentives for bio-based materials in the sector
	5	Apply carbon tax on all fashion products (and other products) for GHG emissions in full product delivery chain
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Establishing (markets, free sharing spaces, online platforms)
	2	Regulation
	3	Incentives
	4	Incentives
	5	Quota/Tax
Expected Impact	1	Reduction of reuse rather than disposal
	2	Reduction of waste and primary raw material usage
	3	Certified biobased materials/less land use impacts
	4	Higher percentage of bio-based material in the sector
	5	Reduction of GHG emission from production
Year specified	1	2025
	2	2030
	3	2030
	4	2050
	5	-

Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	End of life
	3	Production
	4	Production
	5	Production

A3.2 Germany

Germany overarching goals

Policy document name	German Resource Efficiency Programme III - 2020 to 2023 (37)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	<p>Further reduction of raw material consumption: 12 t as goal (2018 16,8 t) *aligned to https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/daten/umweltindikatoren/indikator-rohstoffkonsum#die-wichtigsten-fakten)</p> <p>Raise total raw material productivity: 1,5%/a</p> <p>“The goal of greater resource efficiency and resource substitution is to embed the principle of the circular or closed-loop economy in production processes, thus tapping into potentials for emission reduction that have not previously been used.” (NDC referring to resource efficiency program)</p>
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Raise raw material efficiency
Expected Impact	1	Reduction of primary resource usage
Year specified	1	-

D4.1. Report presenting scenarios and related policy packages

Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
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Policy document name	Act to Promote Circular Economy and Safeguard the Environmentally-Compatible Management of Waste (39)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(1) The preparation for the re-use and recycling of municipal waste is to be: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. at least 50 % by weight overall from 1 January 2020 onwards, 2. at least 55 % by weight overall from 1 January 2025 onwards, 3. at least 60 % by weight overall from 1 January 2030 onwards, and 4. at least 65 % by weight overall from 1 January 2035 onwards
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Higher re-use and recycling rate
Year specified	1	2025/2030/2035
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life

Germany construction sector

Policy document name	Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (36)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	Further savings could be achieved across various sectors by reducing indirect emissions, which occur during the production of building materials, components and plant technology, etc. in the industrial sector. In addition to promoting the use of

		<p>resource-efficient building materials, the selective dismantling of buildings and the recycling of building materials could also contribute to reducing energy demand here.</p> <p>The Federal Government will submit an overall strategy for existing building stock in the form of the long-term renovation strategy pursuant to Article 2a of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased funding for research and development projects, specialist and consumer information, competitions of ideas, model / demonstration projects aiming at • climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use • promoting climate-conscious consumer behaviour.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	<p>The Federal Government will submit an overall strategy for existing building stock in the form of the long-term renovation strategy pursuant to Article 2a of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • increased funding for research and development projects, specialist and consumer information, competitions of ideas, model / demonstration projects aiming at • climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use <p>promoting climate-conscious consumer behaviour.</p>
Expected Impact	1	(...) savings could be achieved across various sectors by reducing indirect emissions, which occur during the production of building materials, components and plant technology.
Year specified	1	-
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Act to Promote Circular Economy and Safeguard the Environmentally-Compatible Management of Waste (39)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	70% by weight from 2020 prepared for recycling or other material recovery

Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Increase in separation of material flows
Year specified	1	2020
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life

Germany plastic sector

Policy document name	Verpackungsabfälle (Packaging waste) (42)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	2025: Increase recycling quota for plastics: 3,8%/a 2030: Increase recycling quota for plastics: 8,8%/a
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Reaching goals of the packaging directive EU
Year specified	1	2025/2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life

Germany textile sector

Policy document name	Act to Promote Circular Economy and Safeguard the Environmentally-Compatible Management of Waste (39)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	Separated collection of textiles from 2025
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Regulation
Expected Impact	1	Increase in separation of material flows
Year specified	1	2025
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life

A3.3 Italy

Italy overarching goals

Policy document name	National Strategy for Circular Economy (51, 61)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	the reform of the EPR and Consortia systems to support the achievement of EU targets through the creation of a specific supervisory body, under the presidency of the Ministry of Ecological Transition, to monitor the functioning and the effectiveness of Consortia;
	2	the development of a favourable fiscal system for a circular economy;

	3	the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts;
	4	the development and uptake of methodologies that quantify all environmental impacts over the lifecycle of a product and throughout the waste management system;
	5	skills development for integrating circular economy issues in school curricula and professional training
	6	the development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system;
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Monitor the functioning and effectiveness of consortia evaluating EPR schemes
	2	Provide fiscal and administrative facilities
	3	(...) promoting eco-innovation as a tool for competitiveness and sustainability and identifying tools to develop eco-innovation opportunities within the circular economy. (...) develop taxation supportive of the transition to a circular economy circular economy, to be achieved both by phasing out subsidies that are harmful to the environment
	4	(...) Implementing the principle of Extended Producer Responsibility so that it takes take responsibility for the final fate of the product up to the end-of-life stage, as well as the "Polluter Pays" principle (with schemes of vacuum returnable, pay-per-use, pay-as-you-throw)
	5	(...) introduce incentives in favour of those who promote behaviours individuals aimed at waste reduction, including consumers. (...) designing new consumer education and training programs interdisciplinary to the figure of circular economy expert, with the parallel development of facilities and public-private agreements for the development entrepreneurship in this new sector
	6	(...) competitive in terms of availability, performance and cost by acting on the materials purchasing chain (Minimum Environmental Criteria for Green Procurement in Public Administration), and on the criteria for the cassation of waste status ("End of Waste"). Essential to the creation of market conditions is the issue of traceability of materials and waste.
Expected Impact	1	-
	2	-

	3	-
	4	-
	5	Skills developed
	6	(...) create conditions for a market for secondary raw materials so that they are competitive (...)
Year specified	All	2035
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production
	3	End of life
	4	Production
	5	Production
	6	Production
Policy document name	Bioeconomy in Italy (50)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million)
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	<p>Improving the sustainable production and quality of products in each of the sectors and interconnecting and leveraging the sectors more efficiently</p> <p>i) More investments in R&I, spin offs/start-ups, education, training, and communication,</p> <p>ii) better coordination between regional, national and EU stakeholders/policies,</p>

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		iii) better engagement with the public iv) tailored market development actions.
Expected Impact	1	Increase in employment
Year specified	1	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	National Strategy for Sustainable Development (62)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative		
Goal qualitative description	1	14.1 By 2025, prevent and significantly reduce all forms of marine pollution, in particular from land-based activities, including marine litter and nutrient pollution. 11.6 By 2030, reduce the negative environmental impact per capita of cities, paying particular attention to air quality and the management of municipal and other waste. 12.5 By 2030, significantly reduce waste generation through prevention, reduction, recycling and reuse.
	2	12.2 Achieve sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources by 2030.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	-
Expected Impact	1	Achieving the national contribution for accomplishing the SDGs
	2	Achieving the national contribution for accomplishing the SDGs
Year specified	1	2025/2030
	2	2030

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Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	Production

Policy document name	Plan for the ecological transition (52)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) an annual saving of annual savings of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO ₂ in the non-ETS sectors.
	2	(...) Long-Term Strategy to 2050, amounting to 60% of the cut emissions for the residential and service sector, it is necessary to maintain a rate of retrofitting of buildings of almost 2% per year (...)
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Reduction of energy usage in the non-ETS sectors
	2	Retrofitted building stock and less emissions
Year specified	1	-
	2	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production

Italy construction sector

Policy document name	Plan for the ecological transition (52)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) an annual saving of annual savings of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO ₂ in the non-ETS sectors.
	2	(...) Long-Term Strategy to 2050, amounting to 60% of the cut emissions for the residential and service sector, it is necessary to maintain a rate of retrofitting of buildings of almost 2% per year (...)
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Reduction of energy usage in the non-ETS sectors
	2	Retrofitted building stock and less emissions
Year specified	1	-
	2	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production

Italy plastic sector

Policy document name	Plastic tax (63)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	<p>From implementation 0,45 €/kg for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Single-use plastic items (MACSI) • Semi-finished products including preforms (e.g. sheets, plugs, bottles, films) • Empty and full packages • Not only food and beverage
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Tax
Expected Impact	1	regulate the import and use of single-use plastic products standardized
Year specified	1	2024
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life

Italy textile sector

Policy document name	National recovery and resilience plan (49)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	<p>Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022.</p>

	2	target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through "Textile Hubs"
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Less waste disposal
	2	support the improvement of the separate collection network in textile sector
Year specified	1	2022
	2	2026
Part of the value chain addressed	1	End of life
	2	End of life

A3.4 Netherlands

Netherlands overarching goals

Policy document name	National Circular Economy Programme 2023 - 2030 (31)	
Qualitative	X	
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	(...) reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact: (...) reduction proposal in the EU taxonomy of 50% in 2030 and 75% in 2050 should be elaborated as new measure
	2	Levies for the use of primary fossil raw materials: at national and European level we will explore the possibilities for taxing nonenergetic use of primary fossil raw materials

Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Levies
Expected Impact	1	All this will be done in a responsible way to protect our environment and health. This way, we will bring our use of raw materials back to a level that the Earth can handle.
	2	in order to stimulate the market for secondary raw materials
Year specified	1	2030/2050
	2	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production

Policy document name	Draft update of the National Plan Energy and Climate (32)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	<p>In 2030:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50 %; • greenhouse gas emissions from production process and waste sector have been reduced to 36 Mton CO2 equivalent; (...) • biofeedstocks are considered to be standard
	2	In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Quota

Expected Impact	1	Promoting clean energy technologies, long-term deployment of low-carbon technologies and related carbon transport and storage infrastructure
	2	Promoting clean energy technologies, long-term deployment of low-carbon technologies and related carbon transport and storage infrastructure
Year specified	1	2030
	2	2050
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production

Netherlands construction sector

Policy document name	Expert knowledge without specific policy document reference based on the input of the INSPIRE conference	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Guiding goal: by 2030, the Netherlands will use 50% less primary abiotic raw materials (minerals, metals and fossils).
	2	As many sustainable renewable raw materials are used as possible; products and raw materials are reused; and hardly any waste exists.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	-
Expected Impact	1	Increase in raw material efficiency
	2	Reduction of fossil fuels and wastes
Year specified	1	2030
	2	2050

Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production

Netherlands plastic sector

Policy document name	National Circular Economy Programme 2023 - 2030 (31)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	In 2030, the use of fossil raw materials for plastics will have been halved (compared to 2016) (...) The release of microplastics into the environment will have been reduced by at least 30%.
	2	In 2050 fewer plastics will be used - where this leads to environmental gains. (...) plastics will no longer be made from fossil raw materials, but rather from recycled raw materials, supplemented with secondary and sustainable bio-based raw materials and - over time - from carbon-based raw materials. Microplastics which are intentionally added to products will no longer exist. Emissions of microplastics (secondary or otherwise) into the environment will have been reduced by at least 70%, moreover.
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	to efficiency improvements and the use of mechanical recyclate, chemical recyclate and plastics based on sustainable bio-based raw materials
	2	plastics will no longer be made from fossil raw materials
Expected Impact	1	The ambition to close the plastic loop in 2050 and no longer produce plastics from primary fossil raw materials is an important dot on the horizon.
	2	Reaching the goal of 2050
Year specified	1	2030
	2	2050

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Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production
	2	Production

Policy document name	Draft update of the National Plan Energy and Climate (32)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	The aim is to increase the obligation to 25 % -30 % plastic recycle or bio-based plastic by 2030. (In anticipation of EU legislation, a national obligation for plastic producers to incentivise the uptake of recycled or bio-based plastics will be introduced as of 2027.)
Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
Expected Impact	1	This obligation applies to all plastics produced in the Netherlands and for the Dutch market. Exports are therefore excluded
Year specified	1	2027
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production

Policy document name	Transition Agenda - Circular Economy (46)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	Annual reduction in growth of plastic: 1,5 %/a
	2	Annual increase in discarded plastics: 1,0 %/a

	3	Discarded plastics via route without sorting which are incinerated: 80%	
	4	Discarded plastics via route without sorting which are exported: 2%	
	5	Discarded plastics via route without sorting: 10%	
	6	Sorted plastics as input for mechanical recycling: 50%	
	7	Efficiency of mechanical recycling: 85%	
	8	Chemically-recycled plastics: 10%	
	9	Efficiency of chemical recycling: 60%	
	10	Produced bioplastics: 15%	
	Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Prevention
		2	Prevention
3		-	
4		More supply and demand	
5		Prevention	
6		Better quality, more environmental efficiency	
7		Better quality, more environmental efficiency	
8		More supply and demand	
9		-	
10		More supply and demand	
Expected Impact	1	Annual reduction in growth of plastic	

	2	Less disposal due to increase in products with long(er) lifespan
	3	-
	4	High usage value, effective return systems, litter control, enforcement
	5	Unsorted waste streams will be significantly reduced
	6	Increased quality of sorted plastics leads to more recycling and less incineration
	7	Increased quality of sorted plastics
	8	Growth in chemical recycling
	9	-
	10	Growth in (sustainably) produced bioplastics
	Year specified	All
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Consumption
	2	End of life
	3	End of life
	4	End of life
	5	End of life
	6	End of life
	7	Production
	8	Production
	9	Production

	10	Production
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Netherlands textile sector

Policy document name	National Circular Economy Programme 2023 - 2030 (31)	
Qualitative		
Quantitative	X	
Goal qualitative description	1	<p>2025:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The share of recycled (post-consumer) / sustainable materials in textile products will be 25%. • 30% of resources, materials and products placed on the Dutch textile market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible. • 10% of the textile products placed on the market in the Netherlands will be reused in the Netherlands after collection.
	2	<p>2030:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In all textile products placed on the market in the Netherlands, 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycle and 20% will be sustainable textiles. • 50% of resources, materials and products placed on the Dutch textile market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible. • 15% of the textile products placed on the market in the Netherlands will be reused in the Netherlands after collection.
	3	2035: The aim is to halve the ecological footprint of the textile industry with regard to emissions, water usage, chemicals and microplastics
	4	2050: Fully circular economy
	5	<p>2030 New goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New textiles placed on the market will have a circular design • Textiles will be used twice as long by consumers compared to 2023 • 100% of the textiles where lifetime extension is not possible will be collected and recycled

Mechanism (through which the target should be realised)	1	Quota
	2	Quota
	3	Quota
	4	Quota
	5	Quota
Expected Impact	1	Raw material efficiency increase and more share of recyclate in the markets
	2	Raw material efficiency increase and more share of recyclate in the markets
	3	halve the ecological footprint of the textile industry
	4	Reduction of raw material consumption and sustainable textile industry
	5	55% less impact on climate change; 55% less indirect land use; 50% less impact on eutrophication and acidification
Year specified	1	2025
	2	2030
	3	2035
	4	2050
	5	2030
Part of the value chain addressed	1	Production/End of life
	2	Production/End of life
	3	Production
	4	Production

	5	Production/Consumption
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A4 Policy portfolio scenarios

Table A4 3: Overview of portfolio of selected policy goals for the BioTransition scenario of the overarching EU level addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description						
2023	Annual energy savings obligations by MSs: 2024-2030: >1.5% (20)						
2025	Increasing municipal waste recycling: >55% by weight by 2025 (23)						
2030	(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (26)	At least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency by 2030; Reducing primary (39%) and final (36%) energy consumption by 2030 (20)	Net reduction of GHG emissions by at least 55% (By 2030 vs. 1990 level) (225 million tonnes of CO2 equivalent) (24)	(...) Overall Union renewable energy target to 42,5 % in the energy mix (50)	Restrict landfilling of waste recyclable or suitable for energy recovery (51)	Carbon farming should contribute -42 Mio. t CO2eq to -310 Mio. t LULUCF target (25)	Under EU law, Green Deal ambitions and in synergy with other initiatives, by 2030 the EU should reduce: (...) 6. significantly total waste generation and by 50% residual municipal waste. (22)
2035	Increasing municipal waste recycling: >60% by weight by 2025 (23)						
2050	No net emission of greenhouse gas emissions in EU by 2050 where economic growth is decoupled from resource use (21)	(...) are managing natural resources sustainably, reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, limiting and adapting to climate change and strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs. (1)	(...) 1% increase of European wood-based products in the market share of the global construction, textile and plastics markets could (1)	Air, water and soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with, thus creating a toxic-free environment (22)			

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Table A4 4: Overview of portfolio of selected and more ambitious policy goals for the BioRevolution scenario of the overarching EU level addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description						
2023	Annual energy savings obligations by MSs: 2024-2030: >1.5% (20)						
2025	Increasing municipal waste recycling: >55% by weight by 2025 (23)						
2030	(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (26)	At least 32.5% improvement in energy efficiency by 2030; Reducing primary (39%) and final (36%) energy consumption by 2030 (20)	Net reduction of GHG emissions by at least 55% (By 2030 vs. 1990 level) (225 million tonnes of CO2 equivalent) (24)	(...) Overall Union renewable energy target to 42,5 % in the energy mix (50)	Restrict landfilling of waste recyclable or suitable for energy recovery (51)	Carbon farming should contribute -42 Mio. t CO2eq to -310 Mio. t LULUCF target (25)	Under EU law, Green Deal ambitions and in synergy with other initiatives, by 2030 the EU should reduce: (...) 6. significantly total waste generation and by 50% residual municipal waste. (22)
2035	Increasing municipal waste recycling: >60% by weight by 2025 (23)						
2040	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> (...) economic growth is decoupled from resource use (21)	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> (...) are managing natural resources sustainably, reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources, limiting and adapting to climate change and strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs. (1)					

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2050	No net emission of greenhouse gas emissions in EU by 2050 (21)	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p>(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) (26)</p> <p><i>To about 1,5% of worldwide market in the sectors of construction, plastics and textiles (adapted (1))</i></p>	Air, water and soil pollution is reduced to levels no longer considered harmful to health and natural ecosystems and that respect the boundaries our planet can cope with, thus creating a toxic-free environment (22)				
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Chemical sector

Table A4 5: Overview of portfolio of selected policy goals for the BioTransition scenario for the chemical sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description			
2028	By 2028, any ton of CO2 captured, transported, used and stored by industries should be reported and accounted by its fossil, biogenic or atmospheric origin; (25)			
2030	At least 20% of the carbon used in the chemical and plastic products should be from sustainable non-fossil sources by 2030, in full consideration of the EU's biodiversity and circular economy objectives and of the upcoming policy framework for bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics. (25)	5 Mt of CO2 should be annually removed from the atmosphere and permanently stored through frontrunner projects by 2030. (25)	(...) reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact: (...) reduction proposal in the EU taxonomy of 50% in 2030 (29)	(...) consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50 % (30)
2050	To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that "Recycled in the EU" becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimised.(...) (28)	0% pollution for air, water, and soil (28)	(...) reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact: (...) and 75% in 2050 should be elaborated as new measure (29)	In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular (30)

Table A4 6: Overview of portfolio of selected and more ambitious policy goals for the BioRevolution scenario for the chemical sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description			
2028	By 2028, any ton of CO2 captured, transported, used and stored by industries should be reported and accounted by its fossil, biogenic or atmospheric origin; (25)			
2030	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p><i>At least 30% of the carbon used in the chemical and plastic products should be from sustainable non-fossil sources by 2030, and of 40% in 2050.</i></p> <p>(...) in full consideration of the EU's biodiversity and circular economy objectives and of the upcoming policy framework for bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics. (25)</p>	5 Mt of CO2 should be annually removed from the atmosphere and permanently stored through frontrunner projects by 2030. (25)	(...) reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact: (...) reduction proposal in the EU taxonomy of 50% in 2030 (29)	(...) consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50 % (30)
2040	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p><i>To move towards toxic-free material cycles and clean recycling and ensure that "Recycled in the EU" becomes a benchmark worldwide, it is necessary to ensure that substances of concern in products and recycled materials are minimised.(...) (28)</i></p>			
2045	0% pollution for air, water, and soil (28)			

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2050	(...) reducing the raw material footprint coupled with reduction of the environmental impact: (...) and 75% in 2050 should be elaborated as new measure (29)	In 2050, industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular (30)		
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Construction sector

Table A4 7: Overview of portfolio of selected policy goals for the BioTransition scenario for the construction sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description					
2023	Article 11 (2a) "(...) (b) by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;" (23)	4. The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. (...) maximum total amounts of primary raw material used: (c) for bio-based materials, a maximum of 80% (...) come from primary raw material; (e) for non-biobased plastic, a maximum of 50% of the total material come from primary raw material; (40)	5. The use of primary raw material in the renovation of the building is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. (...) maximum amount of primary raw material used: (c) for bio-based materials, a maximum of 90% of the material come from primary raw material; (e) for non-biobased plastic, a maximum of 75% of the material come from primary raw material; (40)	4. The preparing for re-use or recycling of (...) construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. (...) Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled. (40)	GER: 70% by weight from 2020 prepared for recycling or other material recovery (60)	GER: Raise total raw material productivity 1,5%/a (35)
2030	At least 2% of annual energy renovation (33)	(...) double their annual energy savings obligations, leading the way by action throughout the public sector. (...) renovate 3% of their buildings' floor space annually. (20)	(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink. (26)	GER: will submit an overall strategy for existing building stock in the form of the long-term renovation strategy • climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use (34)		
2050	Each Member State shall establish a long-term renovation strategy to support the renovation of the national stock of residential and non-residential buildings, decarbonised building stock by 2050 (...) (55)					

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Table A4 8: Overview of portfolio of selected and more ambitious policy goals for the BioRevolution scenario for the chemical sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description									
2023	Article 11 (2a) "(...) (b) by 2020, the preparing for re-use, recycling and other material recovery shall be increased to a minimum of 70 % by weight;" (23)	GER: 70% by weight from 2020 prepared for recycling or other material recovery (60)	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>GER: Raise total raw material productivity: 2%/a (35)</i></p>							
2025	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>specific capacity buildings activities for the professionals and raise their awareness</i></p>									

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<p>2030</p>	<p>At least 2% of annual energy renovation (33)</p> <p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>That includes obligation for insulation of all rented houses</i></p>	<p>(...) double their annual energy savings obligations, leading the way by action throughout the public sector. (...) renovate 3% of their buildings' floor space annually. (20)</p>	<p>(...) role of wood products is to help turn the construction sector from a source of greenhouse gas emissions into a carbon sink. (26)</p>	<p>GER: will submit an overall strategy for existing building stock in the form of the long-term renovation strategy • climate-friendly and innovative timber usage, especially in the area of building with wood, and in relation to the re-use of hardwood timber, the circular economy and cascading use (34)</p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>5 Mt of CO2 should be annually removed from the atmosphere and permanently stored through frontrunner projects by 2030. (25)</i></p> <p><i>(including vacancy management of buildings)</i></p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>The use of primary raw material in the construction is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. (...) maximum total amounts of primary raw material used: (c) for bio-based materials, a maximum of 80% (...) come from primary raw material; (e) for non-biobased plastic, a maximum of 50% of the total material come from primary raw material; (40)</i></p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>The use of primary raw material in the renovation of the building is minimised through the use of secondary raw materials. (...) maximum amount of primary raw material used: (c) for bio-based materials, a maximum of 90% of the material come from primary raw material; (e) for non-biobased plastic, a maximum of 75% of the material come from primary raw material; (40)</i></p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>The preparing for re-use or recycling of (...) construction and demolition waste generated on the construction site is at least 90%. (...) Alternatively, at least 95% of the mineral fraction and 70% of the non-mineral fraction of the non-hazardous demolition waste is separately collected and prepared for reuse or recycled. (40)</i></p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>Establishment of a (mandatory) Digital Product Passport for construction products on European level with - besides others - information regarding repair, reuse, recycling as well as biomass content.</i></p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal</i></p> <p><i>Guiding goal: by 2030, the Netherlands will use 50% less primary abiotic raw materials (minerals, metals and fossils).</i></p>
<p>2050</p>	<p>Each Member State shall establish a long-term renovation strategy to support the renovation of the national stock of residential and non-residential buildings, decarbonised building stock by 2050 (...) (55)</p>	<p><i>Adapted policy goal:</i></p> <p>(...) Increase of market share for wood products for the support of reaching climate goals (...) (26)</p> <p><i>To about 1,5% of worldwide market in the sectors of construction, plastics and textiles</i></p>	<p><i>Adapted policy goal:</i></p> <p><i>as many sustainable renewable raw materials are used as possible; products and raw materials are reused; and hardly any waste exists.</i></p>							

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Plastic sector

Table A4 9: Overview of portfolio of selected policy goals for the BioTransition scenario for the plastic sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description				
2023	Article 5 (5) (...) lower the sum of concentration levels of lead, cadmium, mercury and hexavalent chromium resulting from substances present in packaging or packaging components (...) (39)	"Article 11 (1) " (...) member states shall set up separate collection at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass, (...) (23)	Article 5 Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic. (38)	1. The activity complies with one of the following criteria: (a) use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging (40)	GER: Raise total raw material productivity 1,5%/a (35)
2025	Article 46 (1) Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets (a) by 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated; (b) by 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood; (39)	Article 6 (5) With regard to beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex: (a) from 2025, beverage bottles (...) manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (...) (38)	Article 11 (1) " (...) member states shall set up separate collection (...) (23)	GER: Increase recycling quota for plastics: 3,8%/a (37)	
2028	1. The activity complies with one of the following criteria: From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging; (a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight	Article 6 (5) (...) (b) from 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (...) (38)			

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	consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (40)				
2030	Article 6 (3) Recyclable packaging shall, from 1 January 2030, comply with the design for recycling criteria as laid down in the delegated acts adopted pursuant to paragraph 4 and, (39)	Article 7 (1) From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component; (b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (39)	Article 38 (1) Each Member State shall reduce the packaging waste generated per capita, by (a) 5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040 (39)	Article 46 (1) Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets (c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated; (d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated: (i) 55 % of plastic; (ii) 30 % of wood; (39)	GER: Increase recycling quota for plastics: 8,8%/a (37)
2035	Article 6 (3) from 1 January 2035, also with the recyclability at scale requirements (39)				
2040	2. From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b); (39)				

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Table A4 10: Overview of portfolio of selected and more ambitious policy goals for the BioRevolution scenario for the plastic sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy goal description						
2023	Article 5 (5) (...) lower the sum of concentration levels of lead, cadmium, mercury and hexavalent chromium resulting from substances present in packaging or packaging components (...) (39)	"Article 11 (1) " (...) member states shall set up separate collection at least for paper, metal, plastic and glass, (...) (23)	Article 5 Member States shall prohibit the placing on the market of the single-use plastic products listed in Part B of the Annex and of products made from oxo-degradable plastic. (38)	1. The activity complies with one of the following criteria: (a) use of circular feedstock: until 2028, at least 35% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for non-contact sensitive packaging and at least 10% for contact sensitive packaging (40)	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>GER: Raise total raw material productivity: 2%/a (35)</i>		
2025	Article 46 (1) Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets (a) by 31 December 2025, a minimum of 65 % by weight of all packaging waste generated; (b) by 31 December 2025, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated: (i) 50 % of plastic; (ii) 25 % of wood; (39)	Article 6 (5) With regard to beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex: (a) from 2025, beverage bottles (...) manufactured from polyethylene terephthalate as the major component ('PET bottles') contain at least 25 % recycled plastic (...) (38)	Article 11 (1) " (...) member states shall set up separate collection (...) (23)	GER: Increase recycling quota for plastics: 3,8%/a (37)	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>Article 6 (3) Recyclable packaging shall, from 1 January 2030, comply with the design for recycling criteria as laid down in the delegated acts adopted pursuant to paragraph 4 and, (39)</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>Annual reduction in growth of plastic: 1,5 %/a (42)</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>Article 6 (3) Recyclable packaging shall, from 1 January 2030, comply with the design for recycling criteria as laid down in the delegated acts adopted pursuant to paragraph 4 and, (39)</i>

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2028	<p><i>1. The activity complies with one of the following criteria: From 2028, at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of recycled post-consumer material for noncontact sensitive packaging and at least 50% for contact sensitive packaging; (a) use of bio-waste feedstock: at least 65% of the packaging product by weight consists of sustainable bio-waste feedstock (40)</i></p>	<p>Article 6 (5) (...) (b) from 2030, beverage bottles listed in Part F of the Annex contain at least 30 % recycled plastic (...) (38)</p>					
2030	<p>Article 7 (1) From 1 January 2030, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging: (a) 30 % for contact sensitive packaging made from polyethylene terephthalate (PET) as the major component; (b) 10 % for contact sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except single use plastic beverage bottles; (c) 30 % for single use plastic beverage bottles; (d) 35 % for packaging other than those referred to in points (a), (b) and (c) (39)</p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p>Article 46 (1) Member States shall take the necessary measures to attain the following recycling targets</p> <p>(c) by 31 December 2030, a minimum of 70 % by weight of all packaging waste generated; (d) by 31 December 2030, the following minimum percentages by weight of the following specific materials contained in packaging waste generated: (39)</p> <p><i>(i) 60 % of plastic; (ii) 35 % of wood;</i></p>	<p>GER: Increase recycling quota for plastics: 8,8%/a (37)</p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p><i>Article 38 (1) Each Member State shall reduce the plastic waste generated per capita, by</i></p> <p><i>(a) 7,5 % by 2030; (b) 10 % by 2035; (c) 15 % by 2040 (39)</i></p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p><i>less use of plastics in agriculture (mulch films, foil tunnels ect.)</i></p>		
2035	<p>Article 6 (3) from 1 January 2035, also with the recyclability at scale requirements (39)</p>						

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2040	<p>2. From 1 January 2040, the plastic part in packaging shall contain the following minimum percentage of recycled content recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, per unit of packaging:</p> <p>(a) 50 % for contact sensitive plastic packaging, except single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(b) 65 % for single use plastic beverage bottles;</p> <p>(c) 65 % for plastic packaging other than those referred to in points (a) and (b); (39)</p>	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p><i>Mechanical recycling: 45% and chemical recycling of 15% (adapted of (27, 42)</i></p>					
2050	<p><i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i></p> <p><i>As much as possible no fossil based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU)</i></p>						

Textile sector

Table A4 11: Overview of portfolio of selected policy goals for the BioTransition scenario for the textile sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy objective description					
2023	ITA: Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022. (45)	ITA: (...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO2 in the non-ETS sectors. (48)				
2025	Article 11 (1) " (...) member states shall set up separate collection (...) and, by 1 January 2025, for textiles" (23)					
2026	Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through "Textile Hubs" (45)					
2030	"establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects." (44)	"(...) to support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products" (44)	ITA: Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (46)			

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2035	ITA: the reform of the EPR and Consortia systems to support the achievement of EU targets through the creation of a specific supervisory body, under the presidency of the Ministry of Ecological Transition, to monitor the functioning and the effectiveness of Consortia;(47)	ITA: the development of a favourable fiscal system for a circular economy;(47)	ITA: the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts;(47)	ITA: the development and uptake of methodologies that quantify all environmental impacts over the lifecycle of a product and throughout the waste management system;(47)	ITA: skills development for integrating circular economy issues in school curricula and professional training(47)	ITA: the development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system;(47)
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Table A4 12: Overview of portfolio of selected and more ambitious policy goals for the BioRevolution scenario for the textile sector addressing circular biobased economy aspects

Year	Policy objective description							
2023	ITA: Directive 851/2018 provides that for textiles, EU Member States have to establish separate collection by 1 January 2025. Italy, with Legislative Decree No. 116/2020, in transposing the provisions of the Directive, brought forward the deadline to 1 January 2022. (45)	ITA: (...) an annual saving of 20 Ktoe of energy and 0.04 MtCO2 in the non-ETS sectors. (48)						
2025	Article 11 (1) " (...) member states shall set up separate collection (...) and, by 1 January 2025, for textiles" (23)	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>Fortify local / regional infrastructures to enable sharing of textiles (or other resources) (markets, free sharing spaces, online platforms)</i>						
2026	Target of 100% recovery in the textile sector, through "Textile Hubs" (45)							
2027	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>The share of recycled (post-consumer) / sustainable materials in textile products will be 25%.</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>30% of resources, materials and products placed on the textile market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible.</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>10% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused after collection.</i>					

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2030	"establishes the framework for setting eco-design requirements for specific product categories in order to improve their circularity, energy performance and other environmental sustainability aspects." (44)	"(...) to support its uptake among producers and to offer consumers an easily recognisable and reliable way to choose eco-friendly products" (44)	ITA: Increase by 20% the current output of the Italian bioeconomy (about €250 billion/year) and employment level (about 1.7 million) (46)	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>In all textile products placed on the market 50% sustainable materials will have been used. Of that 50% at least 30% will be recycled and 20% will be sustainable textiles.</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>50% of resources, materials and products placed on the market will be recycled after collection - if direct reuse is no longer possible.</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>15% of the textile products placed on the market will be reused in the after collection.</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertilizer)</i>
2035	ITA: the reform of the EPR and Consortia systems to support the achievement of EU targets through the creation of a specific supervisory body, under the presidency of the Ministry of Ecological Transition, to monitor the functioning and the effectiveness of Consortia;(47)	ITA: the development of a favourable fiscal system for a circular economy;(47)	ITA: the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as eco-design and extending the lifespan of products and parts;(47)	ITA: the development and uptake of methodologies that quantify all environmental impacts over the lifecycle of a product and throughout the waste management system;(47)	ITA: skills development for integrating circular economy issues in school curricula and professional training(47)	ITA: the development of secondary markets for raw materials supported by a clear framework for the supply of secondary raw materials and by an improved waste traceability system;(47)	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>The aim is to halve the ecological footprint of the textile industry with regard to emissions, water usage, chemicals and microplastics</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>Apply carbon tax on all fashion products (and other products) for GHG emissions in full product delivery chain</i>
2050	<i>Adapted or added policy goal:</i> <i>Full circular textile material flows</i>	<i>Adapted or added policy goal</i> <i>Increase incentives for bio-based materials in the sector</i>						